

LAUDS FACTORIES

Deliverable 2.2 –

**Technical and Organizational Readiness Framework for
Facilitating LAUDS Manufacturing**

October 2025

Authors

Fedoua Kasmi (UL)

Michel Langhammer (HSU)

Review and approval status

	Name and Surname	Role in the Project	Partner
Author(s)	Fedoua Kasmi	Lead researcher	UL
	Michel Langhammer	Lead researcher	HSU
Reviewed by	Jean-Francois Boujout	Senior researcher	GINP
	Malte Hertz Jansen	Practitioner	MAK
Approved by	Robert Mies	Project coordinator	TUB

History of changes

Version	Date	Description of changes	By
0.1	01.05.2025	Start initial draft, technical background	Fedoua Kasmi, Michel Langhammer
0.2	01.06.2025	Added cross-analysis, per case analysis	Fedoua Kasmi, Michel Langhammer
0.3	01.08.2025	Added conclusion, Discussions, Introduction	Fedoua Kasmi, Michel Langhammer
1.0	01.10.2025	Final formatting, Version for review	Fedoua Kasmi, Michel Langhammer
1.1	31.10.2025	Revised version after review from Jean-Francois Boujout and Malte Hertz Jansen	Fedoua Kasmi, Michel Langhammer

Details

Dissemination level	Open Access
Due date	30.06.2025
Issue date	31.10.2025
Contract No.	869984
Responsible Partner	HSU

Keywords

Urban Manufacturing, Urban Factories, Distributed Manufacturing, Technical Readiness, Open Production

Summary

This deliverable introduces a novel three-layer technical readiness framework encompassing physical, digital, and organisational infrastructure for the assessment of urban manufacturing facilities. Empirical analysis across eight European case studies confirms that these infrastructures are highly accessible, adaptable, and foster collaboration within community-driven ecosystems. Nevertheless, persistent bottlenecks such as space saturation, fragmented digital workflows, and weak formalisation of quality and planning procedures constrain the capacity to reliably scale projects from prototyping to consistent small-scale production. The findings articulate targeted recommendations that adapt technical infrastructures of existent makerspaces, FabLabs, and third places to optimize alignment with circular, open, and urban manufacturing paradigms.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Theoretical background	7
2.1 Urban factories as enablers of sustainable and urban manufacturing	7
2.3 Collaborative innovation spaces as urban and creative factories.	8
3. Conceptual readiness framework for LAUDS manufacturing	10
3.1. Physical infrastructure layer	10
3.2. Digital infrastructure layer	13
3.3 Organisation of technical infrastructure	15
4. Data collection and analysis	17
4.1 Used digital toolchain	17
4.2 Data collection	17
4.3 Data analysis	19
4.4 Recommendation framework	20
5. Results: Cross-case analysis of technical infrastructure	22
5.1 Synthesis of physical infrastructure	23
5.1.1 Space	25
5.1.2 Machines & equipment	27
5.1.3 Operations	30
5.1.4 Energy	32
5.1.5 Recommendations – physical infrastructure	33
5.2 Synthesis of digital infrastructure capacity	34
5.2.1 Digital tools	35
5.2.2 Data management	39
5.2.3 Data monitoring	40
5.2.4 Recommendations – Digital infrastructure	41
5.3 Synthesis of organisational infrastructure	42
5.3.1 Manufacturing structure	44
5.3.2 Project planning and coordination	45
5.3.3 Supply chain management	46
5.3.4 Quality control and process improvement	48
5.3.5 Knowledge management	48
5.3.6 Recommendations – Organisational infrastructure	49
6. Discussion	50
7. Conclusion	51
References	53
Appendix	55
Appendix 1. Example of individual report – Maker V10 (Copenhagen, Denmark)	55
Physical infrastructure readiness	56
Digital infrastructure readiness	59
Organizational infrastructure readiness	61
Appendix 2.a Survey questionnaire - Form	64
Appendix 2.b Survey questionnaire - Interview	84

List of figures

- Figure 1: Framework structure for analysing the readiness of technical infrastructure 10
- Figure 2: Digital whiteboard with refined framework elements from conducted focus group workshop in Porto, October 2024..... 19
- Figure 3: Snapshot of code tree with code frequency by categories, codes and coder 20
- Figure 4: Bubble chart of relative distribution of machine quantity and processes 27
- Figure 5: Heatmap of machine counts across processes 27
- Figure 6: Radar of digital tool integration score..... 37
- Figure 7: Radar of automation score..... 38
- Figure 8: Screenshots from website of MAKER..... 55
- Figure 9: Spacelayout of MAKER 56
- Figure 10: Distribution of existent equipment processes at MAKER V-10..... 57

List of tables

- Table 1: Overview of participating case-settings 18
- Table 2: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of physical infrastructure 23
- Table 3: List of quotes on intuitive operation of machines in each LAUDS Factory 28
- Table 4: Recommendation matrix for physical infrastructure 33
- Table 5: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of digital infrastructure 34
- Table 6: CAX mapping of digital tools in use 36
- Table 7: Recommendation matrix for digital infrastructure 41
- Table 8: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of organisational infrastructure 42
- Table 9: Matrix of implemented circular practices across LAUDS Factories..... 47
- Table 10: Recommendation matrix for organisational infrastructure 49

1. Introduction

This deliverable is part of Task 2.2 entitled **Analysis of existing digital and physical infrastructures in the representative ecosystems** of Work Package (WP) 2 “Digital and physical infrastructure to enable LAUDS manufacturing”. It focuses on analysing the technical infrastructure readiness of LAUDS Factories (8 case settings). Its primary objective is to examine how local production ecosystems are equipped across three layers (physical, digital, and organisational) and to identify strengths and weaknesses that affect their capacity to support experimentation, development, and scale-up of manufacturing projects by artists, creatives, entrepreneurs, and small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The task combines an ecosystem perspective with a focus on used equipment and operational practices, allowing us to understand both technical capabilities and organisational routines.

Within WP2, Task 2.2 is closely articulated with Task 2.1 “Derive technical capacities and process requirements for LAUDS manufacturing” (WP2) and Task 1.2 “Developing a local readiness level scale” (WP1), ensuring continuity and complementarity with T3.4 “Consolidated LAUDS framework” (WP3). Task 2.1 identifies and assesses user needs as well as the technical capacities and process requirements necessary for LAUDS manufacturing, providing the methodological and functional reference for evaluating how infrastructures enable these functions in practice. Task 1.2, on the other hand, developed the Collaborative Capacity Maturity Model (C2M2) to assess the preparedness of local projects operating within the LAUDS Factories. In this context, Task 2.2 focuses on the readiness of the technical infrastructure including factory spaces, their physical configurations, digital systems and organisational structures that make such projects possible. Together, these tasks establish a multi-level understanding of readiness, linking the user and functional dimension (T2.1), the infrastructural and organisational focus (T2.2), and the project and community perspective (T1.2).

To achieve this objective, the deliverable developed and implemented a three-layer conceptual readiness framework, a novel contribution of the LAUDS project to literature. The framework provides an analytical structure to capture infrastructure capacities in terms of physical resources (such as machines, spaces, operations), digital tools (such as data management, resource tracking, collaborative platforms), and organisational practices (such as governance, planning, stakeholder integration, quality assurance). Data were collected in eight case study factories across Europe, representing diverse ecosystems like makerspaces, FabLabs, community-driven initiatives, and semi-industrial hubs. A mixed-methods approach was applied, combining a detailed questionnaire (87 items) with in-depth semi-structured interviews targeting managers, technical staff, and users. Interview transcripts and survey responses were analysed through thematic coding using the three-layer framework, enabling both systematic comparison and sensitivity to context-specific conditions.

The outcomes of this task serve two purposes within LAUDS Factory project. First, they provide a comparative cross-case analysis of current infrastructure readiness of the LAUDS Factories across Europe, highlighting recurring strengths such as accessibility, openness, and adaptability, but also revealing persistent bottlenecks such as space saturation, machine dependence, fragmented digital practices, and informal organisational routines. Second, the task develops a recommendation framework structured around change management categories (start doing, keep doing, leverage, watch) that offers incremental, practical measures for strengthening LAUDS Factories as resilient, inclusive, and future-oriented infrastructures.

This deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the theoretical foundations of urban factories. Section 3 proposes a conceptual framework of infrastructure readiness, outlining key categories and criteria to be analysed. Section 4 details the methodology, including data collection and coding processes. Section 5 presents the cross-case analysis of infrastructure capacities along the three-layer framework. Section 6 discusses the findings in relation to existing debates and practical implications. Section 7 concludes by summarising key insights, outlining limitations, and identifying directions for future research.

2. Theoretical background

Note: The following section is based on a conference paper that is currently being processed in the Springer's Book Series "Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering": KASMI, F; LANGHAMMER, M; HILLY A; MIES, R, **Technical and organizational readiness framework for facilitating development of sustainable manufacturing processes by urban and creative factories**. *21st Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing*. September 10 - 12, 2025 Bologna, Italy.

While globalization has driven technological progress, it has also led to the outsourcing of manual labour, technical knowledge, and industrial innovation away from urban centres, intensifying the environmental impact of mass production. In response to these challenges sustainable and urban manufacturing practices involves rethinking traditional factories to fit the city context pursuing the triple bottom line (economic, environmental, social goals) within a compact, diverse community-integrated footprint. Technological advances have made this feasible: new processes are smaller, quieter, and less polluting, enabling factories to operate in cities with minimised disturbance. This document proposes a framework for assessing and supporting the physical, digital and organisational capabilities of urban and creative factories, highlighting their potential to enable sustainable small-scale manufacturing in the urban context, supporting small and medium-sized manufacturers and creatives.

2.1 Urban factories as enablers of sustainable and urban manufacturing

Within the wider urban manufacturing literature, urban factories or micro-factories have emerged as enablers of distributed and small-scale manufacturing. The precise definition of an "urban factory" remains rather vague, reflecting the nascent stage of this development and the diversity of its manifestations (Ijassi et al., 2022; Juraschek et al., 2018). However, three main characteristics emerge systematically from the literature:

Integration into urban areas

Typically, urban factories are flexible production facilities embedded in densely populated areas, contrasting with the traditional separation of manufacturing from residential zones (Herrmann et al., 2020; Abdoli, 2019). Their integration into urban ecosystems provides distinct advantages: proximity to customers, suppliers, and skilled labour; access to existing infrastructure and the ability to implement localized product-service systems (e.g. on-demand production for local needs) (Meyer et al., 2023; Tsui et al., 2021; Rudolf, 2023). These factories often repurpose industrial buildings or adopt multi-story designs to maximize limited space (Frey, 2020).

Localized circular urban production

A key aspect of sustainable urban manufacturing lies in the integration of circular economy principles, where urban waste streams become reused resources in local production cycles (Tsui et al., 2021). In this context, urban factories can be designed by exploiting the city's "urban metabolism", notably through the use of materials from urban mines (e.g. electronic waste, demolition scrap, plastic waste...), as well as by-products from local industries (Meyer et al., 2023). This approach creates synergistic exchanges on an urban scale, where local waste streams become raw materials valorised

by the urban factory in a circular logic. This perspective includes not only manufacturing processes, but also the supply of raw materials, distribution of finished products and waste management while actively engaging local stakeholders throughout the value chain (Meyer et al., 2023; Ijassi, 2023).

Digitalization and smart technologies integration

Urban micro-factories are increasingly adopting Industry 4.0 technologies, forming the basis of the “urban smart factory” (Sajadieh, 2022). These tools help maximize productivity and adaptability within spatial and resource constraints. IoT systems enable real-time monitoring of equipment and energy use and the reconfigurable manufacturing setups and collaborative robots (cobots) support custom, small-batch production in compact environments (Amjad & Diaz-Elsayed, 2024). Digital platforms for networked distributed manufacturing like CAx software along the product lifecycle allow global collaboration and local fabrication. Due to the increasing complexity and number of interacting systems a need for seamless data exchange and integration is required with overcoming technical challenges such as data connectivity and message formats using established standards and protocols. To achieve a higher level of interoperability, semantic models and ontologies support a common understanding of the meaning of data and to enable true collaboration (Vernadat et al., 2025).

Furthermore, emerging tools such as Digital Product Passports (DPPs) improve traceability and circular economy compliance through secure, data-driven documentation of lifecycle activities. Finally, dynamic scheduling systems can help a distributed network of urban workshops coordinate production and share workloads or resources. These innovations echo the notion of “smart cities” integrating urban production with smart grids (for energy), intelligent logistics, and digital marketplaces.

Conclusively, urban factories provide solutions to a number of problems encountered in urban areas, addressing supply chain disruptions, carbon emissions, and inefficient resource use through localised, flexible production. They promote circular economy practices by transforming urban waste into inputs and repurposing existing infrastructure, and foster inclusive urban development by creating local jobs and engaging communities. This vision of urban factories, as we will see in the next section, is also aligned with the New European Bauhaus initiative and the Industry 5.0.2.2 Industry 5.0 and New European Bauhaus: Toward Human-Centric, Creative Urban Factories

Beyond the Industry 4.0 paradigm, Industry 5.0 and the New European Bauhaus (NEB) are shaping the next generation of urban manufacturing in Europe. Industry 5.0, as defined by the European Commission, prioritizes human-centricity, sustainability and resilience (European Commission, 2024). It promotes collaborative workplaces where humans and robots co-create, and where production is circular by design, with the well-being of workers and the community representing a central consideration. For urban contexts, this means micro-factories that are open, flexible and integrated into the local dynamic. The NEB initiative, launched in 2021, brings a cultural and aesthetic perspective, calling for environments that are “beautiful, sustainable, together”. Applied to manufacturing, the NEB principles inspire factory workshops that combine functionality with artistic vision, inclusivity and urban integration, imagining factories as places of innovation, creativity and civic value.

2.3 Collaborative innovation spaces as urban and creative factories.

Collaborative spaces like Makerspaces, FabLabs (sometimes taking the form of third places or third dimension places) can play a role as creative, distributed manufacturing environments in cities. These are open-access workshops equipped with digital fabrication tools (e.g. 3D printers, CNC machines,

laser cutters) that enable individuals and small firms to turn ideas into physical prototypes or products (Tsui et al., 2021). They foster collaboration and community engagement by operating as community resources where people share equipment, knowledge, and skills (Morel et al, 2018; García-Ruiz & Lena-Acebo, 2022). This openness and peer production culture strengthen the sense of community and can drive grassroots innovation (García-Ruiz & Lena-Acebo, 2022). In Europe, makerspaces and FabLabs serve as innovation hubs where art, design, and technology can converge, reflecting New European Bauhaus values (Fab City Foundation, 2025). They have the potential to function as “urban workshops” of Industry 5.0, democratizing manufacturing and anchoring production in local communities.

However, despite their potential, the role of makerspaces and FabLabs in local production systems remains underexplored. For instance, Hennelly et al. (2019) examined various types of makerspaces and found that they are predominantly focused on educational (type 1) or design-related (type 2) activities, rather than on actual production functions (type 3). Several significant challenges explain the limited emergence of production-oriented makerspaces. First, there is a predominant emphasis on educational outcomes and community engagement, which often leads to infrastructure setups inadequate for production. The physical spaces and equipment, tailored mainly towards prototyping or learning, typically lack the precision, reliability, and scalability needed for consistent product manufacturing. Additionally, most makerspaces are financially supported through grants, donations, or membership fees, which do not provide a stable financial basis for industrial-scale production (Hennelly et al., 2019; Meyer, 2023).

Scaling up these spaces requires consideration of infrastructure development. Meyer et al. (2023) highlights the critical role of providing suitable and purpose-designed facilities that cater explicitly to production needs, thus increasing the ability to interact with the local urban ecosystem, reducing external dependencies and generating economic value directly through material transformation. This involves ensuring consistent access to necessary resources, including energy, water, specialized materials, and technology capable of handling variant production demands and complexities. Moreover, Hausleitner et al., (2022) emphasize the necessity of robust logistics systems for efficient material flow, supply chain integration, and waste management, which are fundamental for achieving operational sustainability and economic viability in constrained urban settings.

3. Conceptual readiness framework for LAUDS manufacturing

The characteristics of urban manufacturing highlighted in the literature underscore infrastructure needs: adaptable, modular spaces and multifunctional equipment suited to constrained urban environments (physical); robust digital capabilities for managing data, connectivity, and automation in small-scale manufacturing (digital); and organisational capacities necessary for effectively governing local circular supply chains and facilitating distributed collaboration (organisational).

Figure 1: Framework structure for analysing the readiness of technical infrastructure

These insights form the foundation of the framework’s structure, which underpins the readiness analysis in section 4. In the following the components with its attributes are described in detail.

3.1. Physical infrastructure layer

01 Physical Infrastructure
 This layer assesses the tangible, spatial, and technical foundations that enable urban factories to operate effectively within compact and often constrained metropolitan environments. Physical readiness captures the capacity of facilities to host and sustain production activities by considering the adaptability of space, the performance and sustainability of energy and utilities, the operational flexibility of layouts, and the suitability of machines and equipment for small-batch, customised manufacturing. In the context of urban manufacturing, where real estate is scarce and regulatory

pressures on noise, emissions, and safety are high, physical infrastructure must be modular, energy-efficient, and capable of reconfiguration to serve both prototyping and small-scale production needs (Ijassi et al., 2022; Sajadieh et al., 2022). High physical readiness ensures that collaborative factories can support diverse user groups (makers, SMEs, artists, and innovators) without compromising operational continuity, sustainability goals, or compliance with local urban constraints.

01.a Space

Space adaptability and versatility

This sub-criterion assesses how easily an urban factory can accommodate diversified activities, from prototyping to small-batch production, using modular layouts, reconfigurable workstations, and interchangeable zones. High adaptability maximises operational continuity in limited footprints and supports co-creation by enabling rapid reorganisation to suit different projects (Herrmann et al., 2020; Ijassi et al., 2022). This flexibility is central to distributed manufacturing networks, allowing sites to pivot production in response to local demand (Meyer et al., 2023).

Space accessibility

Accessibility refers to both physical entry and opportunities for experimentation and collaboration, ensuring the space is inclusive for professionals, SMEs, artists, and hobbyists. In practice, this means barrier-free access, clear wayfinding, open lab policies, and flexible booking systems. Lowering access barriers fosters innovation and diversifies participation.

Urban integration

Urban integration considers the proximity of the facility to densely populated areas, along with its ability to operate without causing disruption (noise, dust, safety risks). Factories well integrated into their neighbourhoods benefit from short supply chains, access to skilled labour, and stronger ties to local creative ecosystems (Hausleitner et al., 2022). Solutions include low-emission machinery, architectural noise control, and active community engagement (Herrmann et al., 2020).

01.b Machines & equipment

Multi-functionality and versatility

Assesses the extent to which machines support rapid transitions from prototyping to small-series production, minimising changeover time and floor-space demands. High readiness is characterised by hybrid or modular equipment (e.g., CNC with automatic tool-changing (ATC) and fixture libraries; additive systems paired with subtractive finishing; integrated material handling or in-process inspection) that can be redeployed across projects without extensive reconfiguration. In urban factories, such versatility improves throughput in constrained spaces, enables Do-It-Together workflows (co-creation and open manufacturing processes), and supports local circular loops by processing secondary materials with minimal extra kit (Herrmann et al., 2020; Tsui et al., 2021). It also underpins distributed manufacturing resilience by allowing sites to pivot between products as local demand shifts (Meyer et al., 2023).

Machine accessibility

Evaluates how intuitive, safe, and inclusive machines are for mixed user groups (makers, SMEs, artists, hobbyists...), consistent with LAUDS' "Accessible" and Industry 5.0's human-centricity. It includes clear HMIs, guided job setup, low training time, embedded safety interlocks, and standard operating

procedures. User-friendly, intuitive machines lower training time and broaden participation (Sajadieh et al., 2022; García-Ruiz & Lena-Acebo, 2022).

Openness of machines

Machines that are well-documented, repairable, and modifiable reduce lifecycle costs, increase uptime, and foster collaborative problem-solving. Open-source hardware principles (Redlich et al., 2015) enable community maintenance and knowledge sharing.

01.c Operations

Material handling

In compact urban factories, efficient material handling is vital for maintaining workflow. Material handling encompasses the storage, movement, and accessibility of raw materials, in-process items, and finished products within the facility. Efficient handling systems (such as vertical storage racks, labelled shelving, or compact automated retrieval) minimise space usage and improve workflow in space-constrained factories (Jariwala, 2021).

Maintenance and internal capacity for reliability

Proactive, in-house maintenance capacity ensures that machines operate reliably with minimal external intervention. When urban factories have the tools, spare parts, and skilled personnel to perform routine servicing and minor repairs, they reduce downtime and dependency on external service providers (Jariwala, 2021). This internal capability is particularly important in multi-functional environments where a single machine may serve multiple purposes; breakdowns can otherwise create bottlenecks across several production processes.

Equipment reconfiguration

Equipment reconfiguration refers to the ability to adjust and rearrange workstations to suit different stages of production, from early concept prototyping to small-batch finishing. Flexible workstation layouts (achieved through mobile benches, modular fixtures, and quick-connect utilities) allow urban factories to adapt quickly to project changes and co-creation activities (Sakao et al., 2024). This operational agility aligns with the Industry 5.0 emphasis on human-centric and adaptive production systems.

Material management

Material management covers the sourcing, storage, and availability of standard materials for users. Providing centralised access to common stock, such as sheets, filaments, or recycled inputs, reduces lead times and enables experimentation without costly procurement delays (Herrmann et al., 2019). In circular manufacturing contexts, effective material management also includes integrating secondary raw materials and coordinating with local suppliers to minimise transport-related environmental impacts (Meyer et al., 2023).

Adaptation and flexibility

Adaptation and flexibility in operations refers to the capacity to adjust product design and manufacturing steps based on user feedback, co-creation processes, and changes in demand. This is a hallmark of small-batch urban manufacturing, where lines must be retooled rapidly to accommodate customised orders (El Maraghy & Wiendahl, 2009). Close interaction with end-users enables iterative

prototyping and design refinement, supporting participatory approaches in which the customer is actively involved in shaping the product (Manzini & Rizzo, 2011).

01.d Energy

Renewable energy sources

This sub-criterion evaluates whether renewable energy is integrated into the facility's supply, either through on-site generation (e.g., rooftop solar panels, small wind turbines) or procurement from certified renewable providers. In small-scale urban factories, renewable integration can help mitigate grid dependency, stabilise long-term costs, and demonstrate environmental leadership to the community (Sajadieh & Noh, 2024). On-site generation may be limited by available roof space or building regulations, but partnerships with local renewable cooperatives or purchasing agreements can still provide a viable path toward low-carbon energy sourcing.

Energy efficiency

Measures such as machine-level energy monitoring, idle-time shutdowns, and high-efficiency lighting systems can significantly reduce consumption in high-demand environments. In shared workshops, energy tracking can also help distribute costs fairly among users and encourage off-peak operation (Sajadieh & Noh, 2024).

3.2. Digital infrastructure layer

02 Digital Infrastructure

The digital layer assesses the integration, usability, and openness of digital systems that support manufacturing operations in urban factories. In small-series, distributed production environments, digital infrastructure enables co-creation, networked collaboration, and efficient use of shared resources (Amjad & Diaz-Elsayed, 2024). It is not only about deploying advanced tools but ensuring they are accessible to both professional and non-professional users in co-working production spaces, while supporting interoperability and open standards to enhance adaptability (Vetter, 2018; Redlich et al., 2015).

02.a Digital tools

Integration

Integration measures how seamlessly digital tools are connected across design, prototyping, and production stages. In high-readiness environments, CAD/CAM, production scheduling, and IoT-based monitoring systems exchange data without manual transfers, enabling a continuous flow of information (Vernadat et al., 2020). This reduces errors, shortens lead times, and supports distributed manufacturing models by allowing multiple sites to access the same up-to-date project data (Amjad & Diaz-Elsayed, 2024).

Automation

Automation readiness reflects the degree to which workflows, such as toolpath generation, machine setup, and quality inspection, are digitally managed without repeated human intervention. Automation frees up operator time and enables small teams to manage more processes simultaneously (Herrmann et al., 2020; Barni et al., 2017). Examples include automated nesting in fabrication software or linked sensor data that triggers process adjustments in real time.

Accessibility

Digital tools must be intuitive enough to serve users with varying technical expertise. Makerspaces and shared workshops often combine experienced fabricators with newcomers; accessible interfaces, and onboarding tutorials are essential to inclusive participation (Vetter, 2018). Accessibility also includes the availability of low-barrier licensing models or shared workstations to ensure that software costs do not exclude smaller actors.

Openness

Open-source or openly documented digital tools reduce dependency on proprietary systems, enabling local adaptation, repair, and integration into diverse hardware setups (Redlich et al., 2015; Directorate-General for Communications Networks, 2021). For urban factories, openness fosters collaboration within local innovation ecosystems and allows distributed networks to replicate workflows across sites.

Adaptation and flexibility

Digital adaptation refers to the interoperability of tools and file formats. Design files can be easily transferred between software platforms or fabrication tools without losing data integrity, supporting collaborative, multi-site projects (Lopes & Barata, 2024; Vetter, 2018). Flexible systems allow urban factories to work with diverse partners and respond to rapidly changing project requirements.

02.b Data management

Data sharing

Proactive data sharing involves making relevant project, process, or performance information accessible to collaborators while respecting privacy and IP agreements. In distributed manufacturing networks, this strengthens coordination and enables cumulative learning across sites (Abubakar, 2024). In makerspaces, shared knowledge bases and open repositories are particularly valuable for training and replication.

Storage & file system

Structured data storage and the use of centralised repositories ensure that digital assets are securely stored and easily retrieved. Integration with version control and metadata systems reduces duplication and errors (Sajadieh, Son, & Noh, 2022). In shared urban facilities, clear storage protocols help avoid file loss in multi-user environments (Abubakar, 2024).

02.c Data monitoring

Process tracking

Automated monitoring of machine metrics, energy use, and resource consumption supports both operational efficiency and sustainability evaluation. In high-readiness spaces, IoT sensors and software dashboards allow managers to track utilisation rates, detect faults early, and generate data for sustainability reporting (Abubakar, 2024; Sajadieh, Son, & Noh, 2022).

Network connectivity

Network connectivity describes access to the internet, the local factory network and available machine data connections. Reliable local networking and internet access are prerequisites for digital collaboration and cloud-based design or production control. In distributed urban manufacturing, connectivity ensures remote access to machines, synchronisation of project files, and participation in

multi-site workflows (Abubakar, 2024). This is critical for resilience, especially when facilities operate as nodes in a broader production ecosystem.

3.3 Organisation of technical infrastructure

03. Organisational Readiness Layer

The organisational readiness layer evaluates the structures, processes, and relationships that enable an urban factory to operate efficiently, adapt to change, and deliver value in small-series, distributed manufacturing contexts. While the physical and digital layers address what the facility has, the organisational layer focuses on how it is governed, coordinated, and connected to partners, networks, and local ecosystems. It considers governance models, collaboration capacity, planning and coordination processes, supply chain integration, quality control, and knowledge management; ensuring the factory can respond effectively to opportunities and challenges while pursuing sustainable and innovative production (Redlich et al., 2015; Grubbauer, Manganelli, & Volont, 2024).

03.a Manufacturing structure

Distributed governance

Distributed governance refers to the capacity for autonomous decision-making within different manufacturing activities or project streams. This enables multiple work areas or teams to progress without delays from centralised control, while still aligning with the facility's overall strategy (Redlich et al., 2015). Such governance structures help maintain flexibility and responsiveness in a variety of operational contexts.

Inter-organisational collaboration

Readiness in inter-organisational collaboration is demonstrated by strong networks both within the facility and with external partners, including suppliers, clients, research organisations, and civic actors. These relationships underpin the distributed manufacturing model and make it possible to deliver complex, multi-actor projects efficiently (Wulfsberg, Redlich, & Bruhns, 2010; Marche et al, 2023; Savastano, Bellini, & D'Ascenzo, 2023).

03.b Project planning and coordination

Integration

Integration in project planning involves aligning operational timelines with longer-term strategic objectives, ensuring that activities across the facility are coherent and mutually reinforcing. This supports stability and coordinated growth while allowing room for innovation (Hildebrandt, Redlich, & Wulfsberg, 2021; Abdoli et al., 2019).

Information sharing

Proactive information sharing ensures that relevant project updates, technical resources, and operational data are easily accessible to those who need them. Clear channels for communication, whether digital or in-person, help avoid duplication of work and support efficient collaboration (Abdoli et al., 2019).

Process adaptation and flexibility

High process flexibility allows for rapid reconfiguration of workflows, resources, and priorities in response to changing project requirements or external conditions. This capability is essential for small-series manufacturing where production variables may shift frequently (Herrmann et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2020).

03.c Supply chain management

Local supply chain

Factories with well-developed local supply chains can shorten lead times, reduce transport-related emissions, and strengthen regional economies. Readiness in this area is indicated by the ability to source most inputs within clearly defined geographical ranges (local, regional, continental, or global) with a preference for the local short supply chains (Hausleitner et al., 2022; Meyer et al., 2023).

Stakeholders' integration

Stakeholder integration involves actively involving relevant actors in co-design, production, and decision-making processes. This can include co-location, collaborative planning, and open design platforms that promote transparency and alignment of interests through a Do-It-Together approach (Marche et al., 2023; Ijassi et al., 2024).

Circularity

Embedding circular economy principles throughout operations, such as material reuse, waste minimisation, and sustainable sourcing, improves resource efficiency and aligns with wider sustainability goals. Readiness here includes processes, practices and partnerships that enable systematic implementation of these principles (Tsui et al., 2021; Kasmi et al., 2022; Elwakil et al., 2023).

03.d Quality control and process improvement

Quality measurement system

A formal quality measurement system (either certified or internally documented) consistent outcomes and supports trust among partners and clients. Readiness is demonstrated by the presence of clear protocols, measurable performance indicators, and continuous improvement mechanisms (Markert et al., 2024).

03.e Knowledge management

Knowledge transfer

Knowledge transfer readiness refers to the processes in place to share operational expertise, technical know-how, and best practices. This includes structured training, peer-to-peer learning, and accessible documentation that collectively enhance the facility's operational and technological capabilities (Krenz et al., 2014).

4. Data collection and analysis

This chapter delineates the processes employed for data collection and explores the methodologies utilized to gather qualitative and quantitative data.

4.1 Used digital toolchain

Following digital tools and services were used for the performance of T2.2

- EU Survey tool¹ (online survey tool)
- QualCoder² (qualitative data analysis tool)
- Jupyter Notebook³ (Interactive computing framework)
- Excalidraw⁴ (collaborative digital whiteboard tool)

The **EU Survey tool** provided by the European Commission facilitates the design and execution of surveys, incorporating analytical capabilities for data evaluation. **QualCoder** is an open-source qualitative data analysis (QDA) tool, providing researchers with a platform to code and analyse textual information. **Jupyter Notebook** offers an interactive environment that supports multiple programming languages, enabling code execution and rendering of visualizations seamlessly. **Excalidraw** offers a collaborative drawing platform, enabling real-time creation of diagrams and sketches, enhancing visual communication in virtual team settings. Collectively, these tools exemplify advancements in open research methodology and collaborative frameworks in academic contexts.

4.2 Data collection

The study was conducted with seven case-settings declared as LAUDS Factories (Spain, Germany, France, Denmark, Ukraine, Switzerland), representing diverse collaborative settings such as makerspaces, FabLabs, and third places. The eighth case-setting MEKANIKA represents a machine builder manufacturer based in Brussels, Belgium, not declared as a LAUDS Factory but considered in this analysis due to its existent medium-batch manufacturing workflows. To capture different perspectives within each factory, the data collection typically targeted three profiles: the factory manager, the technical manager, and an active user (e.g. maker). This mixed approach was well suited to the exploratory nature of the readiness concept and the heterogeneity of urban factory contexts, allowing both systematic comparison and context-sensitive refinement of criteria. Following table gives an overview of the participating case studies.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>

² <https://qualcoder.wordpress.com/>

³ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁴ <https://excalidraw.com/>

Table 1: Overview of participating case-settings

Name	Acronym	City	Country	LAUDS	Profiles
Maker V-10	MAKER	Copenhagen	Denmark	yes	Manager, Technician
Taller para la Materialización y el Desarrollo de (grandes) Conceptos	TMDC	Barcelona	Spain	yes	Manager, Technician, User
METALAB POLE	META	Ivano-Frankivsk	Ukraine	yes	Manager, Technician
Fab City Hamburg	FCHH	Hamburg	Germany	yes	Manager
FabLab SUPSI	SUPSI	Lugano	Switzerland	yes	Manager
Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	BUW	Weimar	Germany	yes	Manager
Lorraine Fab Living Lab	UL	Nancy	France	yes	Manager, Technician
MEKANIKA	MEK	Brussels	Belgium	no	Technician

The elements and criteria for the readiness framework were first identified through a structured review of relevant literature and refined in a focus group workshop with consortium participants (researchers, managers, and makers).

WP2 – Workshop Session – Case-Setting Analysis

feedback on T2.2 survey – questions

Questions:

- what areas to consider
- what to leave out
- where to focus

feedback on T2.2 survey – readiness assesement

Questions:

- is the readiness grid representing the current (T1.1 output) LAUDS target?

Assessing the readiness of technical infrastructures involves evaluating how well these infrastructures are able to:

- support current and future operations; adapt to changes;
- leverage opportunities for improvement and innovation;
- ensure the infrastructure can handle growth or new initiatives.

groups of 2 for each section

Figure 2: Digital whiteboard with refined framework elements from conducted focus group workshop in Porto, October 2024

Between January and March 2025, data collection combined two sources: (1) an electronic questionnaire with 87 items, and (2) semi-structured interviews of 2–3 hours per site. The survey questions are provided in Appendix 2.a Survey questionnaire - Form and Appendix 2.b Survey questionnaire - Interview. The survey provided structured evidence on infrastructure practices, while the interviews offered deeper qualitative insight into operational challenges and strategic priorities.

4.3 Data analysis

Interview transcripts and survey responses were coded and thematically analysed by three researchers from UL and HSU using QDA software QualCoder. Coding followed the three-layer conceptual framework (physical, digital, and organisational infrastructure) with sub-dimensions identified from the literature (Figure 1). Codes were applied inductively within these categories, producing weighted values that reflect the relative emphasis placed on different themes across cases.

The coding outputs were then merged with the questionnaire results to generate individual factory reports. The case of MAKER serves as an exemplary factory report and can be found in Appendix 1. Example of individual report – Maker V10 (Copenhagen, Denmark). The other cases can be found at the "Lauds factories - Horizon Europe project" Zenodo repository⁵. Each report describes the three

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/lauds/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

infrastructure layers in detail. From these reports, a comparative matrix of strengths and limitations was developed, highlighting cross-case patterns of readiness and areas for improvement. Figure 3 visualises the distribution and weight of coded responses (by coder: Anaelle, Fedoua, Michel) mapped to the framework's dimensions.

Code Tree	Anaelle	Fedoua	Michel	Total	Code Tree	Anaelle	Fedoua	Michel	Total
01 Physical Infrastructure	158	358	347	863	01 Physical Infrastructure	158	358	347	863
Energy Efficiency	6	36	16	58	02 Digital Infrastructure	57	237	136	430
Energy Efficiency	6	30	7	43	03 Organizational Infrastructure	111	324	179	614
Renewable Energy Sources	0	6	9	15	Knowledge Management	15	84	35	134
Machine & Equipment	51	113	98	262	Knowledge Transfer	15	84	35	134
Machine Accessibility	25	56	23	104	Manufacturing Structure	31	50	48	129
Multi-Functionality	2	14	37	53	Distributed Governance	0	10	10	20
Openness of Machine	16	13	33	62	Inter-Organizational Collaboration	31	40	38	109
Reliability	8	30	5	43	Project Planning and Coordination	32	154	70	256
Operations	76	176	168	420	Processes Adaption & Flexibility	16	84	24	124
Adaptation & Flexibility	46	81	71	198	Project Planning Integration	16	70	46	132
Equipment Reconfiguration	5	24	22	51	Quality Control and Process Improvement	5	0	0	5
Maintenance	13	49	68	130	Quality Measurement System	5	0	0	5
Material Handling	12	22	7	41	Supply-Chain Management	28	36	26	90
Space	25	33	65	123	Circularity	6	6	1	13
Integration into Urban Area	3	14	19	36	Local Supply-Chain	3	13	2	18
Space Accessibility	11	6	11	28	Stakeholders Integration	19	17	23	59
Space Adaptability & Versatility	11	13	35	59					
02 Digital Infrastructure	57	237	136	430					
Data Management	10	9	17	36					
Data Sharing	5	6	4	15					
Storage & File Systems	5	3	13	21					
Data Monitoring	6	42	29	77					
Network Connectivity	3	31	5	39					
Process Tracking	3	11	24	38					
Digital Tools	41	186	90	317					
Digital Tool Accessibility	6	23	12	41					
Digital Tool Adaption & Flexibility	6	12	8	26					
Digital Tool Automation	2	18	3	23					
Integration	18	114	44	176					
Openness of Digital Tools	9	19	23	51					

Figure 3: Snapshot of code tree with code frequency by categories, codes and coder

Larger segments indicate greater emphasis in the qualitative material, providing an empirical grounding for the framework and showing how frequently different aspects of infrastructure readiness were discussed.

4.4 Recommendation framework

On this basis, we developed a set of recommendations aimed at strengthening the LAUDS Factories as infrastructures that are both technically resilient and socially inclusive. These recommendations are based not only on the cross-case analysis of the physical, digital, and organisational layers, but also on the documented needs of real users from Deliverable 2.1 (WP2), in particular creatives, artists, and small entrepreneurs who often lack access to professional-grade manufacturing tools, workspaces, and collaborative networks. The objective is not large-scale reconstruction but practical, incremental measures. To structure the proposals, we applied a change management lens with four categories:

- **Start doing:** address urgent gaps where practices are absent or underdeveloped.
- **Keep doing:** consolidate strengths that already deliver value.
- **Leverage:** build on assets that can be scaled or shared.
- **Watch:** monitor risks that could undermine resilience or inclusivity.

This structure highlights not only what actions are needed, but also how they fit into the broader transformation of the factories. By combining a capacity-oriented perspective (efficiency, resilience, scaling) with a user-oriented one (accessibility, affordability, creative empowerment), the

recommendations ensure that LAUDS Factories continue to evolve as open, innovative, and sustainable hubs serving both urban manufacturing demands and the aspirations of creative and entrepreneurial communities.

5. Results: Cross-case analysis of technical infrastructure

The results presented in this section combine evidence from the questionnaires and the coded interviews, offering a comparative picture of the capacities and limitations of the seven LAUDS Factories (and MEKANIKA). The analysis is structured around the three layers of the conceptual framework (physical, digital, and organisational) each of which was explored in depth through coding of the interviews and triangulated with survey data.

The coding distribution (see Figure 3) highlights where emphasis falls across cases. Physical infrastructure emerged as the most prominent theme, reflecting the centrality of space, machines, and daily operations in shaping readiness. Digital infrastructure was less frequently discussed overall, with strong focus on digital tool adoption but weaker signals in data management and monitoring. Organisational infrastructure took an intermediate position where collaboration and coordination practices were well established, but formalization in areas such as quality assurance and supply-chain systems was less visible.

Taken together, these patterns indicate that LAUDS Factories are adaptive in their everyday functioning, but uneven in their ability to sustain resilience under scaling pressures. Strengths are most evident in prototyping capacity, openness, and collaboration, while fragilities appear in space saturation, machine bottlenecks, and the absence of systematic monitoring or quality routines.

The following subsections present a cross-case synthesis for each infrastructure layer. For each, the main strengths and limits across factories are described with examples from individual sites and summarized in table view marked with following colour code:

- **Green:** high readiness,
- **Yellow:** medium readiness,
- **Red:** low readiness

Each subsection concludes with key findings that informed the recommendations. The first part addresses physical infrastructure, followed by digital and organisational layers.

5.1 Synthesis of physical infrastructure

The physical infrastructure of the LAUDS Factories is generally well aligned with prototyping and small-batch production but shows fragility when scaling to higher volumes or managing peaks. Spatially, most sites use modular layouts and multi-zone configurations that support versatility and parallel workflows, yet congestion and storage limits are near-universal bottlenecks. Machine infrastructure is broadly solid, with all but one site equipped with the core CNC, laser cutter and 3D-printer machine toolkit and inclusive training systems that enable both professional and beginner access. However, multifunctionality and automation remain limited, and bottlenecks on high-demand machines persist. Operational practices are functional, with in-house maintenance and flexible reconfiguration enabling adaptability, though material handling and pro-active maintenance routines are inconsistently formalised, leaving systems vulnerable under stress. Energy is the least mature dimension with only a minority of sites integrate renewable energy sources or systematic energy monitoring but most treating these as future plans rather than current practice. Overall, the factories demonstrate strong readiness for diverse prototyping and agile workflows, but their resilience under peak demand depends on improvements in congestion management, preventive maintenance, structured material management, and energy monitoring.

Table 2: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of physical infrastructure

LAUDS Factory	Space	Machines & equipment	Operations	Energy efficiency
MAKER (Copenhagen)	1,000 m ² , well-zoned & reconfigurable; but limited expansion & urban rent/regulation pressures	Diverse equipment setup; accessible via training; in-house repair; open-source contributions; minor bottlenecks at peak	Regular servicing & storage system; but workspace congestion & mostly manual handling	District heating baseline; no renewables; no machine-level monitoring
TMDC (Barcelona)	5,000 m ² modular space; expansion planned (10–15k m ²); strong urban integration; only constraint: ground-level availability	CNCs, KUKA robot, experimental concrete printing; 3D knitting machine; user-friendly; open modification culture;	In-house technician; proactive maintenance; storage & flexible reconfiguration; bottlenecks	Efficient baseline (no HVAC, shared use reduces footprint); plans for rooftop solar & dust extraction

		minor bottlenecks (shared planer)	addressed with booking rules	automation; no current renewables
METALAB (Ivano-Frankivsk)	1,700 m ² ; diverse workshops; urban integration; but bottlenecks when education & production overlap; limited modularity	Versatile universal tools & DIY open-source machines; but limited specialization & frequent “fine-tuning”	Strong internal maintenance; centralized sourcing evolving; but clashes between events & production	"Smart House" electricity system; plans for upgrades; manual energy consumption tracking & no renewables yet
FCHH (Hamburg)	Distributed FabLab network; strong urban integration; limited scale & volunteer dependence	CNCs, laser cutters, 3D printers, cobot; mix of DIY + commercial; versatile; robustness issues	Volunteer based maintenance; supports small-batch (e.g. 50–100 units cell phones); but reactive, ad hoc repairs	Combined heat & power; solar roof potential unused; starting with energy monitoring
SUPSI (Lugano)	3 main rooms; flexible workshop; good accessibility; but physically small, limited expansion	CNC w/ ATC, KUKA robot, open-source 3D-printers; versatile, experimental setups	Light proactive maintenance; flexible for 1–30 unit batches; proactive scheduling; minor reliance on external warranty services	No renewables; no tracking; sustainability mainly addressed in design phase
BUW (Weimar)	Bio lab + planned FabLab space; reconfigurable for art/experiments; access limited by university rules	Small machine setup; DIY + modified machines;	Flexible/adaptive for unique projects; but reliant on wider university workshops for some needs	No renewables; energy-saving mostly behavioural (turning off hoods, reusing glassware)
UL (Nancy)	Restricted space, but highly reconfigurable; strong urban integration; space limits scale	3D printers, CNC, laser cutters; strong open-source culture; limited multi-functionality	Internal maintenance; flexible ad hoc use; but bottlenecks from space & staff shortages	No renewables; small tracking attempts; mostly reactive efficiency actions
MEKANIKA (Brussels)	Warehouse overcrowded; R&D & production clashing; relocation planned	Open-source CNCs; highly user-friendly; accessible via training; strong documentation & repairability	Strong internal maintenance; adaptive supply chain; flexible with last-minute orders	No systematic energy tracking; only passive building measures & awareness

5.1.1 Space

Space adaptability and versatility

The survey responses indicate that spatial configurations are broadly adaptable for prototyping and small-batch production in the LAUDS Factories, but scaling is consistently limited by congestion, storage capacity, and overlapping activities. Seven of the eight factories report using distinct zones for different project types, which supports parallel use and reduces the need for constant re-setting. The examples show how zoning strategies vary but serve similar purposes. MAKER, with its more than ten distinct areas across 1,000 m², demonstrates how extensive subdivision can enable diverse activities to run side by side. SUPSI, though smaller, achieves the same effect by splitting its space into three rooms with clear functional divisions (laser cutter and CNC, robotics and 3D printing, and electronics). By contrast, BUW operate mainly from a single biolab, it must rely on neighbouring university workshops for heavier fabrication. These contrasts highlight that versatility is less a question of size and more about how space is structured and managed.

Constraints emerge clearly in the data. Six of the eight factories reported space occupancy as a frequent bottleneck, five highlighted shortages of skilled personnel, and three noted machine congestion. The fact that half of the sites have 15 or more people working on site daily while others operate with leaner teams explains why saturation occurs quickly during peaks. Even with multiple zones, crowded aisles, benches, and temporary storage can stall production, especially when education and production overlap in academic contexts. Distributed layouts mitigate but do not eliminate these pressures. TMDC, which operates across thirteen warehouses, reduces congestion within individual units but faces coordination costs when material, staff, and tools must converge. This trade-off reflects a broader finding that adaptability is generally robust for day-to-day making, yet capacity to scale is fragile. The limiting factor is not the presence of zones but their saturation under peak conditions.

Space accessibility

Accessibility is deliberately open across the surveyed factories, but the mechanisms used to manage it vary. Five of the eight sites have introduced formal booking or machine access systems (FabManager, Fabman, Cobot, or custom-built tools), while the others rely more on staff oversight and locally agreed procedures. This divergence reflects different operating contexts. In busier environments, automation and scheduling reduce conflicts, whereas in smaller or more research-driven settings, trust and direct supervision are sufficient. Patterns in user density help explain these differences. The results indicate that four factories host 15 or more people on site daily, three have 10 or fewer, and one has only a fractional presence. Where density is high, structured booking systems reduce competition for critical tools and help maintain order. In leaner sites, less formal systems work without generating friction, since simultaneous demand is limited. Contrasts between sites underline this logic. MAKER, for instance, prioritises spontaneity by offering round-the-clock membership access, introducing booking restrictions only for machines that pose higher risks such as CNC. SUPSI, by contrast, ties accessibility to its educational role, with scheduled access aligned to teaching calendars and safety protocols. FCHH adds another variation, coupling open public workshops with an internal machine access system that records usage; an approach that supports accountability in a volunteer-heavy environment. Taken together, the results show that accessibility is not defined by a single model but by the balance between openness, density, and safety requirements. This versatility is a strength, ensuring wide

participation, but it also creates unevenness in readiness. Factories with higher daily traffic have invested in more formalised access systems, while others rely on practices that may be harder to scale if user numbers increase.

Urban integration

Locating factories in dense urban environments brings clear benefits (e.g., short supply chains, proximity to clients and partners, and access to skilled people), but also imposes constraints such as noise, dust, safety regulations, and limited opportunities for expansion. The survey confirms that environmental controls are a routine requirement: six of the eight factories report the need for measures like filtration or housing, four require more advanced protections such as fencing or active noise and emission control, and only two operate without special measures. Examples show how these trade-offs play out in practice. MAKER's relocation to a central city warehouse improved its visibility and proximity to users but also increased exposure to compliance demands and higher rents. TMDC, which actively frames itself as an urban manufacturer, faces the difficulty of securing ground-floor space in a dense fabric, forcing careful planning of assembly and finishing areas to avoid disrupting shared bays. At the same time, FCHH illustrates the opportunities of integration by linking its mission to the city through neighbourhood-scale projects (such as community phone assembly in St. Pauli) and by connecting to municipal infrastructure, including energy networks. The survey also underlines how space constraints translate into operational limits. Six factories report space occupancy as a capacity bottleneck, reflecting the fact that most operate within pre-existing buildings rather than purpose-built facilities. This explains a recurring pattern, the same features that make urban sites attractive (proximity and openness) also restrict their ability to expand. As a result, practical readiness measures are less about rebuilding and more about managing congestion, through annex or overflow areas, stricter rules on project storage, and calendars that schedule large builds without undermining the day-to-day accessibility that urban locations make possible.

Key findings – Space adaptability and versatility

The spatial setup across the eight factories supports agile prototyping and diverse workflows, thanks to modular layouts and multi-zone configurations in most sites. However, while day-to-day adaptability is well established, the ability to absorb peak demand remains limited. Space saturation (more than structural absence) emerges as the primary challenge, especially when educational activities overlap with production or when large builds arrive. Access models vary but generally support openness, and urban settings offer strong ecosystem ties while introducing regulatory complexity. Overall, spatial readiness is functional but under strain, with future resilience depending more on smart coordination than major spatial expansion.

5.1.2 Machines & equipment

Multi-functionality and versatility

The following bubble chart depicts the relative relationship between machine quantity and machine capabilities within used space area (bubble size represents relative space area) across seven LAUDS Factories, providing a comparison indicator of existing technological capacity and versatility.

Figure 4: Bubble chart of relative distribution of machine quantity and processes

Machine availability is broad across the surveyed factories and largely consistent with the expected small-batch production. The results show that six out of seven sites operate the canonical trio of CNC machines, laser cutters, and 3D-printers, usually complemented by woodworking, electronics, and hand tools. This shared baseline allows most factories to handle the majority of prototyping and production tasks in-house, with outsourcing limited to specialised processes. The single exception is BUW, which remains biolab-centric but is developing plans to introduce CNC, laser, and 3D printing to reduce reliance on university workshops. Versatility, however, is uneven. Survey data indicate that half of the sites report only low-level multifunctionality (for example, manual tool changes or limited cross-compatibility) and four explicitly state that they lack multifunctional equipment altogether. Only two sites operate CNCs with automatic tool changers, compressing changeovers and enabling smoother shifts from prototyping to short production runs. Another reported example is the use of a robotic arm for milling, demonstrating selective investment in flexible automation.

Figure 5: Heatmap of machine counts across processes

In the factories, agility is achieved more through policy and scheduling than through high-end capital upgrades. Factories manage versatility by coordinating access and sequencing tasks rather than by relying on advanced multifunctional machines. This approach is effective for day-to-day readiness, but it also suggests that scaling capacity or shifting towards more complex production could be constrained without further investment.

Machine accessibility

Accessibility is high but structured differently across contexts. All eight factories have tiered training systems that allow both beginners and professionals to use equipment. For example, at MAKER, full-sheet CNC and laser cutter access requires mandatory training certificates; SUPSI offers short inductions (1.5 hours for small tools, 3 hours for complex tools). TMDC uses brief workshops for most tools but requires professional training for the KUKA arm; and UL integrates FabManager bookings with written guidelines. FCHH organises introductory workshops aligned with its open community model, while METALAB develops reskilling and education programs. BUW, operating in a university context, combines mentorship with a wiki tool to document machine settings and support users through machine configuration hurdles. Following table shows the qualitative input of each case on the question on “How intuitive is the operation of your machines for users with varying skill levels?”

Table 3: List of quotes on intuitive operation of machines in each LAUDS Factory

Factory	Quotes on intuitive operation of machines for users
MAKER (Copenhagen)	<i>“Clear and visible instructions support the use of our stationary machines and tools. Members and staff have online access to how-to guides, workshop information and training materials via our member platform, Office RnD.”</i>
TMDC (Barcelona)	<i>“Machines are very user friendly. After a few hours of training you can use it on your own. (Apart of the KUKA robot)”</i>
METALAB (Ivano-Frankivsk)	<i>“Everything directly depends on the novelty of the equipment; unfortunately, the old machinery from the factory does not “speak.”</i>
FCHH (Hamburg)	<i>“Depending on the machine/tool. From Beginners to Hobbyist, Students and Professionals”</i>
SUPSI (Lugano)	<i>“We use tools for slicing 3D models that easy to use for designers and people who has at least basics of CAD design”</i>
BUW (Weimar)	<i>“Some tools like microscopes, are intuitive to a certain level. Some tools, like laminar flow hoods or incubators, need some knowledge. But these are still relatively intuitive compared to CNC machines”</i>
UL (Nancy)	<i>“In fact, it depends on the machine! e.g. FDM printer and laser cutter got a high usability; Wood-plastic machines got a moderate and metal machines a low usability”</i>

MEKANIKA (Brussels)	<i>“Not directly on the interface (even if PlanetCNC is pretty straightforward) but we have a lot of content on our support website and blog to start easily with the machine. We also propose training online.”</i>
-------------------------------	--

The survey results confirm this inclusivity: 75% of sites allow beginner access, 87.5% report professional use, and 62.5% also cater to hobbyists. This mix demonstrates a deliberate effort to maintain openness while safeguarding safety and throughput. Despite this inclusive approach, ease of operation is not always optimal. Only one site rated machine intuitiveness at the highest level, while half gave it a moderate score, suggesting that onboarding still depends heavily on structured training rather than on user-friendly design. Formal booking and access-control systems, reported by five of the eight factories, improve accountability and fairness, particularly for high-demand machines. Where no such systems are in place, oversight relies on staff judgement or peer coordination, approaches that preserve spontaneity but risk congestion when activity peaks.

Openness of machines

The survey results show a mixed profile regarding machine openness. Five of the eight factories report using open-source hardware or software, often 3D-printers, machine control units, or machine modifications. At the same time, most sites remain dependent on proprietary systems for certain components or spare parts, indicating that openness is selectively applied rather than universal. Some factories actively design or adapt equipment based on open-source principles (for example, building recycling machines or modifying 3D-printers) to lower costs and simplify repairs. Others focus on using commercially available but well documented machines, supported by in-house expertise that allows staff or members to troubleshoot and extend machine life. One factory, operating as a machine builder (MEKANIKA) is developing its own modifiable open-source hardware machines while integrating closed-source components as not all sub-components are available as open-source. This evidence suggests that openness contributes to resilience by enabling reparability, knowledge sharing, and collaborative problem-solving, but its scope is still uneven for productive reliable usage. In many factories, openness covers entry-level or modular machines, while high-performance assets such as CNCs and laser cutters remain tied to proprietary vendor ecosystems. As a result, lifecycle costs and uptime are partly mitigated by openness but continue to depend on external suppliers for critical tools.

Key findings – Machines and equipment

Machine readiness is broadly solid for prototyping and small-batch production. The core machine toolkit of CNCs, laser cutters, and 3D printers is available in seven sites and covers the majority of processes reported in the survey. Strengths lie in the widespread accessibility of machines, with structured training ladders that allow both beginners and professionals to participate, and in the strong culture of openness, as most factories use open-source hardware and carry out in-house repairs. At the same time, readiness is held back by recurring bottlenecks on high-load machines, limited multifunctionality (only two sites with ATC or robotics), and uneven preventive maintenance, which often remains reactive. In sum, the machine base is functional and inclusive, but future resilience will depend on reducing pressure on critical tools, investing selectively in versatile equipment, and strengthening systematic maintenance practices.

5.1.3 Operations

Material Handling

The survey results indicate that material handling practices are uneven across the factories. Only two of the eight sites report using systematic stock systems, while most rely on ad hoc methods for storing and circulating materials. Four factories maintain shared stocks of standard inputs, and five report regular reuse of materials, showing that while practices for efficiency exist, they are not consistently formalised. MEKANIKA, with its focus on production and demonstration, emphasises well-organised flows of components and finished parts, reflecting its industrial orientation. FCHH, by contrast, encourages experimentation during open workshops, which increases the need for flexible but carefully managed storage to prevent clutter. METALAB, still developing its facilities, extends versatility through improvised handling solutions, often adapting equipment for recycling workflows. These cases highlight how material handling is shaped by operational priorities. The production-oriented sites invest in more structured systems, while community- or experimentation-driven ones accept higher variability in exchange for openness. Constraints emerge strongly in the data. With six of eight factories already reporting space occupancy as a bottleneck, weak or improvised handling systems amplify congestion, particularly during busy periods or when large projects overlap. Without centralised stocks or clear staging areas, raw materials and unfinished work spill into circulation zones, slowing changeovers and raising the risk of conflict over benches and storage space.

Maintenance

The survey results reveal a mixed picture of maintenance practices. Half of the factories report following structured preventive maintenance routines, either weekly or bi-annual, while the others handle servicing more irregularly and reactive. Only one site describes itself as fully independent in maintenance, while most combine in-house troubleshooting with selective reliance on external providers for specialist interventions. Reliability levels are generally good: four factories state that machines operate reliably with only occasional repairs, while the rest experience intermittent downtime, particularly for high-precision or optics-intensive tools such as laser cutters. For example, MAKER has established regular preventive cycles and keeps spare parts on site, which helps limit downtime despite high machine use. TMDC also applies structured routines, covering both weekly checks and longer-cycle servicing, to support its distributed workshop model. In contrast, FCHH relies more heavily on reactive maintenance in its community workshops, which can lead to bottlenecks when a critical machine fails. METALAB, still in an early growth phase, extends the life of its equipment through ad hoc repairs and modifications but lacks formalised routines. These contrasts show that readiness depends not just on technical competence but also on whether procedures are institutionalised and consistently applied.

When preventive routines are absent, downtime multiplies the impact of space bottlenecks already reported by six factories. In multi-functional environments where a single CNC or laser cutter may serve multiple user groups, even short stoppages can disrupt several parallel processes. Globally, maintenance readiness is adequate but uneven. Most sites can repair and service machines internally, yet the maturity of routines varies widely.

Equipment reconfiguration

Most factories are able to reconfigure equipment and workstations to some degree. Six of the eight sites report moderate to high adaptability, enabling them to shift layouts between prototyping, small-

batch production, and educational use. This flexibility is essential in compact facilities where space must serve multiple functions. The factories illustrate different strategies, for example SUPSI makes use of three large rooms that can be rearranged for teaching, prototyping, or collaborative projects, supported by mobile benches and modular fixtures. UL, operating in an academic context, regularly adapts its layouts to balance courses with production needs, though this creates scheduling tensions. MEKANIKA, with a more production-oriented profile, focuses on reconfiguring workstations around demonstrations and short production runs, showing how adaptation can support commercial as well as educational goals. Frequent reconfiguration requires time and staff effort, which can interrupt workflows during busy periods. Survey responses suggest that flexibility often depends on manual movement of benches and tools rather than on fully modular infrastructures, limiting how quickly transitions can occur. In distributed models, such as TMDC's warehouse system, equipment can be moved between units, but coordination costs increase when multiple teams must align their setups. The capability for reconfiguration exists across most sites, but its efficiency is constrained by reliance on manual processes and limited modular infrastructure.

Material management

The survey results indicate that material management remains ad hoc in most factories. Only a quarter of sites report systematic stock systems, while the majority rely on local routines for storing and supplying materials. Around half of the factories provide shared stocks of standard inputs such as sheets or filaments, and a similar proportion report practices for reuse and recycling. This suggests that while the principle of shared access is widely recognised, its implementation is inconsistent. The weakness of material management becomes most visible during periods of high activity. Without structured inventories or centralised stocks, projects risk delays from missing inputs, and temporary storage often overflows into circulation space. These practices exacerbate the space saturation already reported by six factories as a key bottleneck.

Adaptation and flexibility

Adaptability is a defining strength of the LAUDS Factories. Six of the eight report moderate to high capacity to reconfigure operations in response to user needs, project changes, or fluctuating demand. This flexibility underpins the ability to move seamlessly between prototyping, educational activities, and short production runs. The factories frequently adjust production steps to integrate user feedback, modify workstation layouts to accommodate co-creation, and switch quickly between teaching and production contexts. While these shifts are often achieved through manual reconfiguration rather than fully modular infrastructure, the outcome is the same, workflows can be reshaped without long interruptions. At the same time, flexibility has limits, the results show that when demand peaks or large builds arrive, reconfiguration alone cannot compensate for space and resource constraints. Bottlenecks in material handling, storage, and skilled personnel reduce the effectiveness of otherwise agile systems. Flexibility therefore functions best under normal operating conditions, but strains under high loads unless supported by coordinated scheduling and clear rules for prioritisation.

Key findings – Operations

Operations readiness is moderate and enables factories to manage diverse workflows. Flexibility is a key strength as most sites report moderate to high adaptability, allowing them to reconfigure layouts and adjust production steps to accommodate prototyping, education, and small-batch runs. Maintenance capacity is also present, with many factories able to handle repairs in-house, though

practices range from structured preventive routines to largely reactive approaches. At the same time, readiness is weakened by fragmented material handling and management. Only a minority of sites use systematic stock systems, and ad hoc storage often amplifies congestion already identified as a widespread bottleneck. Material management is similarly inconsistent, with shared stocks and reuse practices present but not formalised. Reconfiguration remains possible but depends heavily on manual effort, which slows transitions during peak demand. In sum, operational systems are functional but fragile. They support daily activities effectively, but resilience under stress will require stronger preventive maintenance, more structured handling and inventory practices, and lightweight coordination tools that reduce reliance on ad hoc arrangements.

5.1.4 Energy

Renewable sources

Integration of renewable energy across the eight factories is still at an early stage. MAKER currently operates with district heating at its temporary site and has plans to achieve greater self-sufficiency in future facilities. FCHH benefits from a combined heat-and-power setup at Oberhafen district in Hamburg and has identified strong rooftop solar power potential, though implementation is limited by fire-safety and grid-connection constraints. TMDC has not yet integrated renewables but has prioritised energy management of processes (e.g. intelligent dust extraction control) as a preparatory step. SUPSI reports no current renewable energy integration, with sustainability framed primarily through material and design choices rather than energy sourcing. UL, METALAB, MEKANIKA, and BUW similarly report little or no active renewable energy capacity, although interest in solar or community-energy partnerships is present in interviews. Survey responses confirm this: only 25% of sites report any renewable integration, while the majority describe renewables as a “future plan” rather than a current practice.

Energy efficiency and monitoring

Energy efficiency and monitoring practices are present but unevenly applied. Systematic machine-level metering is rare across the cohort. FCHH demonstrates strong technical potential with its energy and temperature monitoring system, though this data is used more for troubleshooting than for calculating energy indicators. MAKER is aiming to track laser cutter run-times and 3D printer filament use, primarily to inform maintenance and spare-part planning, rather than efficiency metrics. TMDC is preparing on-demand dust extraction controls and stock-linked automation to cut unnecessary energy use. SUPSI monitors air quality as a proxy for environmental performance but does not currently track machine runtime or energy consumption. In the survey, only 2/8 factories report having any form of structured energy-monitoring tools, while the rest operate with either no measurement or very limited ad hoc monitoring. This absence of dashboards linking usage, maintenance, and consumption data represents a clear missed opportunity, especially as Digital Product Passport (DPP) requirements emerge at the EU level.

Key findings – Energy

Energy readiness is incipient across the factories. Only a quarter of sites report any renewable energy integration, with most treating it as a future plan. Efficiency and monitoring are fragmented: just 2/8 sites use structured tools, while most rely on ad hoc practices. The main strength is willingness to experiment (e.g. dust-extraction control, logging platforms, solar potential), but without standardised monitoring, gains remain limited. In short, energy practices are at an early stage, with quick wins

available in plug-level metering and event-based controls, and mid-term opportunities in rooftop PV or green PPAs.

5.1.5 Recommendations – physical infrastructure

The matrix highlights how factories can strengthen both structural capacity and user access.

Table 4: Recommendation matrix for physical infrastructure

Start Doing	Keep Doing
Material management systems (Capacity), Preventive maintenance routines (Capacity), Overflow & storage solutions (Capacity), Energy monitoring and energy efficiency measures (Capacity), Priority booking & residencies for creatives/entrepreneurs (User), Starter packs & shared material libraries (User), Affordable pricing models (User), Mentorship & onboarding programs (User),	Multi-zone layouts (Capacity) Tiered machine training & access (Capacity) Openness of workshops (Capacity) Culture of reuse & repair (Capacity) Prototyping & co-creation zones (User) Inclusive training & onboarding (User) Social hubs & networking spaces (User)
Watch	Leverage
Space saturation during peaks (Capacity), Machine bottlenecks (Capacity), Renewable energy integration gaps (Capacity), Commercial demand crowding out creatives (User), Hidden barriers (fees, booking, training time) (User), Risk of over-professionalisation reducing openness (User)	Open-source practices for machine tools (Capacity), Distributed layouts & modular zoning (Capacity), Community collaboration models (Capacity), Showcases, hackathons, and exhibitions (User), Local partnerships & cultural collaborations (User), Peer-to-peer learning culture (User)

While basic readiness is solid, recurring bottlenecks in congestion, material flows, and machine use call for light but systematic management. On the user side, reducing hidden barriers and preserving openness are as critical as technical upgrades, ensuring that professionalisation does not erode the experimental culture that attracts creatives and small entrepreneurs.

5.2 Synthesis of digital infrastructure capacity

The digital capacity of the LAUDS Factories is inclusive and tool-rich but remains fragmented and largely manual in operation. Across all eight sites, CAD and CAM systems, booking platforms, and cloud collaboration tools are widely in use, ensuring accessibility for diverse user groups through short training modules, QR-coded guides, and modular tutorials. Openness is a defining strength, with six sites deploying open-source tools and five actively contributing back to online repositories, reinforcing adaptability and knowledge exchange across the network. However, integration between systems is weak. Workflows rarely carry a single identifier from design to production, leading to duplicated records and reliance on “shadow spreadsheets,” particularly in university contexts. Automation is at an early stage, with only isolated pilots linking extraction systems or logging machine runtime, and most processes such as stock control, quality assurance, and setup remain manual. Data management practices are functional but inconsistent, cloud storage is universal, yet structured versioning and file protocols are rare, increasing risks of duplication and data loss. Monitoring is the least mature dimension, only two factories systematically track equipment performance, while the majority rely on ad hoc observation. Connectivity itself is strong, supported by urban locations and robust networks, but it is not yet leveraged for real-time monitoring or distributed production control. In sum, digital infrastructure across the factories provides a strong base of accessible tools and collaborative practices, but its potential is undercut by fragmented integration, limited automation, and weak monitoring, leaving significant room for consolidation and scaling.

Table 5: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of digital infrastructure

LAUDS Factory	Digital tools	Data management	Data monitoring
MAKER (Copenhagen)	Use of booking system for critical machines, CAD/CAM and online collaboration; Clear onboarding with guides and checklists; Systems not fully connected; automation almost absent	Cloud storage and team sharing in place; Informal chats and spreadsheets often bypass repositories, no version control	No reliable internet connection; Established monitoring of full sheet CNC usage data linked with billing tool; No monitoring of energy usage yet
TMDC (Barcelona)	Broad use of booking system, CAD/CAM and online collaboration; Active community use; Planning	Data shared via Cobot tool and analog meetings; Informal exchanges	Tested job-linked dust extraction; no machine or energy monitoring

	and invoicing kept separate, automation not established	dominate, record-keeping inconsistent	
METALAB (Ivano-Frankivsk)	Strong design software use (Rhino, Grasshopper, Cura); Flexible for collaborative projects; Limited workflow automation, interoperability gaps	Nextcloud supports structured sharing; Few protocols for versioning, risk of duplication	Good internet connectivity; Minimal process tracking, no lifecycle data tracking
FCHH (Hamburg)	Self-hosted open-source services (LDAP server, MQTT messaging, Grafana dashboard); Strong culture of openness and sharing	Use of self-hosted system for sharing (LDAP server, Nextcloud); Depends on volunteers, uneven structure	Tracking of laser cutter usage; initial energy monitoring system implemented
SUPSI (Lugano)	FabManager and MS Office365 well integrated with teaching; Structured training on tools supports adoption; Still relies on manual workflows; limited automation	Institutional MS OneDrive ensures secure storage; Version control and metadata rarely applied	Strong connectivity; Monitoring of air quality implemented; Machines and energy not digitally monitored
BUW (Weimar)	FabManager plus institutional tools cover teaching needs; Weak integration, no automation	Cloud storage available; Lack of clear protocols, risk of file duplication	Reliable connectivity; No machine connectivity; No monitoring
UL (Nancy)	Uses FabManager and MS Teams, effective for students; Systems run in parallel, no automation	Institutional servers and Teams provide structure; Data redundancy through local spreadsheets, weak file management	Stable institutional network; No machine connectivity; No systematic tracking of processes or machines
MEKANIKA (Brussels)	Integrated digital tools and workflows from design, sourcing and production planning	Cloud storage and git-based system in use; Few structured protocols, informal sharing common	Reliable connectivity; No process or energy monitoring routines

5.2.1 Digital tools

Integration

The following table maps digital tools within the realm of computer-aided technology (CAx), spanning from project management to machine control, including categories such as Business Intelligence (BI), Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Computer-Aided Process Planning (CAPP), Computer-Aided Design (CAD), Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM), and Numerical Control (NC) systems.

Table 6: CAX mapping of digital tools in use

	Management	Collaboration	Planning Tools	Design	Manufacturing	Machine Control
Description	<i>Tool related to space, user, business and project management</i>	<i>Communication, (social) networking, co-developing match-making</i>	<i>Planning and control (e.g. resource-planning tools/ ERP-Systems</i>	<i>Computer-aided 2D, 3D, for product design</i>	<i>Computer-aided manufacturing: incl. CAM-post processor</i>	<i>Machine control software (G-Code interpreter)</i>
CAX Mapping	BI	CRM	CAPP	CAD	CAM	NC-Control
MAKER (Copenhagen)	Office RnD, Economics, Google Drive	Slack WikiFactory	Google Drive	Carbide Create, Illustrator, Rhino, Fusion360, InkScape	Carbide Motion, Fusion360, LightBurn, Prusa Slicer	Masso Control
TMDC (Barcelona)	Cobot	Telegram	Asana	Rhino, AutoCAD, Fusion360, Solidworks, Sketchup	Powermill, SprutCAM, Aspire, Lightburn, Cura Slicer	Planet CNC, KUKA control,
METALAB (Ivano-Frankivsk)	Google Workspace, 1C Accounting Software	Slack, Zoom, Miro, Telegram	N/A	AutoCAD	N/A	N/A
FCHH (Hamburg)	Custom machine access system, Trello	Nextcloud, Element Messenger, Gitlab	Trello	FreeCAD, Fusion360, LibreCAD, Blender, KiCAD.	EdingCNC, Fusion360, FreeCAD, Visicut	EdingCNC, Marlin, Epson laser controller
SUPSI (Lugano)	FabManager	Telegram	Notion	Fusion360	Fusion360	N/A
BUW (Weimar)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
UL (Nancy)	FabManager	MS Teams, Email, Github	N/A	Onshape	Orcaslicer, Trotec Ruby, kiri:Moto	N/A
MEKANIKA (Brussels)	Google Drive	Google Drive, Odoo ERP, Mattermost, Passbolt	Google Sheets, Odoo ERP	Autodesk Fusion360	Autodesk Fusion360	PlanetCNC

Across the eight factories, digital tool adoption is strong, but integration remains patchy. Almost all sites operate CAD and CAM alongside project management and booking platforms, yet these systems are seldom connected into a single workflow.

Figure 6: Radar of digital tool integration across lifecycle activities

As shown in the radar diagram of integration (Figure 6), design and collaboration functions are relatively mature, with MAKER and METALAB reporting strong coverage, while planning, process tracking, and quality assurance lag behind across the cohort. The case narratives confirm this unevenness: TMDC runs Cobot for access and co-working, but billing and project documentation remain separate. FCHH maintains a technically ambitious software stack with LDAP server, MQTT messaging and Grafana dashboarding, but its energy and maintenance data are not yet coupled. UL and SUPSI both use FabManager and Microsoft Teams, but rely on parallel spreadsheets for scheduling and cost attribution. This fragmentation produces duplicated records and parallel “shadow systems,” especially in universities where multiple institutional IT layers co-exist. High-readiness integration, where a single job ID flows from design to booking to machine activation, is still aspirational.

Automation

Automation is the least developed aspect of digital infrastructure. Survey responses show that 6 factories rate their automation level at the very bottom (1/5), a further 2 at level 2, and none beyond level 3. Only 2 report systematic tracking of equipment performance, and most workflows, such as material handling, machine setup, and post-processing, are still managed manually. The automation radar (Figure 2) illustrates this clearly across the cohort.

Figure 7: Radar of automation integration

Nearly all activities remain close to the baseline, with only a few higher scores, for example METALAB reporting more automation in manufacturing steps and MAKER indicating stronger practices in material transport. Case observations provide concrete illustrations of this limited progress. At TMDC in Barcelona, the team experimented with connecting the dust extraction system to the start and stop of machine jobs, so that the extractor would only run when a machine was in use. At Fab City Hamburg, a similar pilot attempted to link the extraction system of a laser cutter to the machine's operating status. Both cases demonstrate the early stages of automation, promising small-scale tests but not yet having become established as everyday routines. For most factories, automation is still restricted to monitoring machine access logs or basic operating-time counters.

Accessibility

Accessibility of digital tools is generally positive, enabling participation from diverse user groups. Survey results indicate that 62.5% of sites require only a one-day introductory course for common tools, while 75% need multi-day practice for advanced CAD/CAM software. MAKER and UL highlight pragmatic onboarding with embedded short tutorials and checklists inside booking systems, reducing staff handholding for large CNCs and robotics. SUPSI provides modular training aligned with academic courses, balancing professional requirements with student learning. Visual interfaces also matter, for example traffic-light booking statuses and QR-coded guides are widely used, lowering barriers for beginners. This inclusivity is essential given the mix of professionals, beginners, hobbyists, and students across the factories. Accessibility thus supports the open, multi-profile ethos of collaborative factories, even if training remains uneven.

Openness

Openness is a defining strength. Six sites report using open-source tools such as FreeCAD, Blender or Linux-based operating systems, and five have contributed schematics, code, or documentation back to

online repositories. FCHH in Hamburg is particularly advanced, running a self-hosted software stack built on open-source tools and sharing learnings with the wider Fab City network. MAKER publishes schematics online, while SUPSI incorporates open-source software in teaching modules. Openness reduces dependency on proprietary systems and enables local adaptation, important in resource-constrained environments. It also strengthens network effects by replicating knowledge and workflows across sites, which is key to distributed manufacturing. The trade-off is reliability, usability and support as several factories still rely on commercial CAD/CAM tools (e.g. SolidWorks, Fusion360), balancing stability with openness.

Adaptation & flexibility

Digital adaptation, understood as the interoperability of file formats and workflows, is moderately developed. All factories use cloud-based storage to exchange files, and three also use git-based repositories. This facilitates collaborative projects across locations. However, versioning and metadata are unevenly applied, and two sites report relying heavily on ad hoc file naming and local servers. Case narratives confirm that while cross-platform design transfers (e.g. from Rhino to Grasshopper to CAM-post processor) are possible but they often require manual checking or file repair. TMDC and METALAB, for example, use a mix of Rhino, Cura, and other local slicers, which complicates seamless flow. Flexibility is nonetheless evident in day-to-day practice as seven factories manage separate zones and teams, and most report being able to adapt workflows rapidly (75% score 4 or 5 on adaptability). The challenge is less about willingness and more about the technical plumbing needed to support multi-site collaboration without data loss.

Key findings - Digital tools

Digital tools are broadly available across the factories, with almost all sites operating CAD and CAM systems, booking and access platforms, and online collaboration suites. Accessibility is ensured through short training courses, embedded checklists, and QR-linked guides, supporting diverse user groups ranging from beginners to professionals. Openness is a shared strength, with six sites relying on open-source tools and five contributing back to community repositories. Yet integration remains fragmented: multiple unconnected systems coexist, and few workflows carry a single identifier from design to production. Automation is still minimal, with most sites reporting only basic logging and occasional pilot projects. Overall, the digital tool environment is rich and inclusive, but fragmented and largely manual.

5.2.2 Data management

Data sharing

Data sharing is widespread but varies in quality. All factories report using digital tools for sharing (Google Drive, Microsoft Teams, Nextcloud, git-based storage), and 62.5% say data are easily searchable and accessible. Six sites use differentiated user roles, while four implement project-specific access rights. Informal sharing remains influential. In-person meetings and ad hoc chats often complement or even bypass digital repositories. Following case examples show this duality: MAKER uses Slack channels extensively but also relies on face-to-face bench discussions. UL integrates MS Teams with institutional servers but acknowledges “shadow spreadsheets” as coordination tools. TMDC leverages Cobot for project allocation but defaults to in-person troubleshooting. This mix reflects both agility and fragility. The projects flow smoothly but the knowledge capture for replication or reporting is inconsistent.

Storage & file system

Cloud storage is universal (8/8), but version control is uneven. Only three sites use git-based repositories, and two maintain local servers. The majority rely on mainstream platforms such as Google Drive, Dropbox, or MS OneDrive, which offer convenience but limited metadata or lifecycle tracking. Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) repositories are rare. Case evidence shows that Nextcloud at METALAB and GitHub or Wikifactory at MAKER support structured collaboration, while SUPSI relies on institutional Microsoft OneDrive with clear user roles. Where no formal protocols exist, duplication and file loss remain risks. In high-density environments with many concurrent users, the absence of structured storage protocols can complicate replication, sustainability reporting, or external auditing or evaluation.

Key findings - Data management

Data sharing is common practice: all factories use digital platforms, and most combine them with in-person meetings. Searchability and access control vary, with some sites applying differentiated user roles while others rely on informal exchanges that bypass repositories. Cloud storage is universal, but only a minority use version control systems such as git or maintain structured local servers. This creates risks of duplication and inconsistent records, particularly in multi-user environments. In sum, data are widely shared and conveniently stored, but protocols for versioning and structured file management are not yet consolidated.

5.2.3 Data monitoring

Process tracking

Process monitoring is incipient. Only two factories track performance metrics systematically, while the rest rely on ad hoc observation or individual logs. The survey shows that 6 factories cluster at level 1 for process data tracking, with no sites reporting more advanced IoT dashboards. Quality monitoring is equally weak, with five sites rating themselves at the lowest level. Case evidence confirms that while machine usage counters are common, these are seldom connected to dashboards. TMDC's dust extraction automation and FCHH's laser cutter vacuum extraction pilot are exceptions but remain isolated. Without systematic process tracking, opportunities for preventive maintenance, cost allocation, or sustainability evaluation and reporting remain limited.

Network connectivity

Internet connectivity is strong, reflecting the urban context. All factories use digital platforms for collaboration, and most combine them with in-person meetings. Cloud storage is universal, and Wi-Fi access is standard. This ensures that files can be synchronised across devices and that remote collaborators can contribute. Case evidence highlights both strengths and fragility. FCHH relies heavily on community-driven platforms that depend on volunteer administration. University labs depend on institutional IT, which can be bureaucratic but robust. TMDC and MAKER emphasise lightweight tools that sustain agility but at the expense of higher subscription fees and low data privacy. Connectivity thus underpins collaboration but is not yet fully leveraged on equipment level for real-time machine monitoring or distributed production control.

Key findings - Data monitoring

Process tracking and monitoring are the least mature digital practices. Only two factories systematically collect equipment performance data, and quality and lifecycle information are rarely digitised. Automation radar scores confirm that most workflows remain at baseline levels of monitoring. Connectivity, however, is strong: all sites use cloud platforms, and most combine them with in-person meetings, ensuring that basic communication is reliable. Thus, factories are well connected for collaboration but still lack systematic digital monitoring of processes, energy use, or quality metrics.

5.2.4 Recommendations – Digital infrastructure

On the digital side, the main structural (capacity) gaps are integration, automation, and monitoring, while users demand seamless prototyping flows, intuitive collaboration tools, and learning support.

Table 7: Recommendation matrix for digital infrastructure

Start Doing	Keep Doing
Integrated workflows (Capacity), Versioning & metadata protocols (Capacity), Scale automation pilots into routines (Capacity), Resource/material dashboards (Capacity), Daily operation systems (User), Compatible prototyping design tools linked to manufacturing (User)	Remote storage & collaboration platforms (Capacity), Short tutorials, QR guides, checklists (Capacity), Open-source tool adoption (Capacity), Inclusive training modules (User), Collaborative groupware (User)
Watch	Leverage
Emerging immersive prototyping (Capacity), Proprietary IT lock-in & shadow systems (Capacity), Complexity barriers in digital systems (User), Tension between professionalisation and openness (User)	Distributed cross-site dashboards (Capacity), Real-time machine data tracking for maintenance & sustainability (Capacity), Open protocols for interoperability (Capacity), Immersive/interactive training (User), Digital showcasing spaces (User),

This matrix aligns both: structural fixes (version control, monitoring, automation) are coupled with user-facing enablers (prototyping software, learning platforms, etc.). The “Watch” space reflects the tension between emerging complex tools and the need to remain inclusive and low-barrier.

5.3 Synthesis of organisational infrastructure

03 Organisation of Technical Infrastructure (5 components)			
03.a Manufacturing Structure: <i>Distributed Governance, Inter-Organisational Collaboration</i>			
03.b Planning & Coordination: <i>Integration, Information Sharing, Process Adaption & Flexibility</i>	03.c Supply-Chain Management: <i>Locality, Circularity, Stakeholder Integration</i>	03.d Quality Control & Improvement: <i>Quality Measurement</i>	03.e Knowledge Management: <i>Knowledge Capturing & Transfer</i>

The organisational capacity of the LAUDS Factories is characterised by strong decentralisation, high adaptability, and dense local networks, but remains weak in formalisation and quality assurance. Governance is largely distributed, with decision-making delegated to teams and members, which supports responsiveness but often relies on informal coordination, making continuity and strategic alignment harder to ensure. Collaboration is a shared strength: six factories actively engage universities, SMEs, artists, and civic actors, embedding themselves in regional ecosystems and anchoring supply-chains locally, while also experimenting with circular practices such as material reuse and recycling. Project planning and coordination are agile but fragmented: information sharing is widely enabled through digital platforms and onboarding tools, yet integration with long-term planning is limited, and reliance on informal or parallel systems is common. Flexibility is consistently high, with most sites able to reconfigure resources quickly to accommodate project changes or shifting user needs. However, quality control and process improvement are the weakest elements: no factory has structured or certified quality assessments (QA), and most rely on peer checks, informal feedback, or ad hoc troubleshooting, which sustains learning but limits readiness for client-facing or scaled production. Knowledge management shows promise, with structured onboarding, peer-to-peer mentoring, and some documentation systems (wikis, tutorials, repositories), but practices remain uneven across sites. In sum, organisational infrastructures enable openness, collaboration, and adaptability, but lack the formalised processes and systematic quality assurance needed to scale production reliably beyond prototyping and education.

Table 8: Strengths and limits matrix for cross-analysis of organisational infrastructure

LAUDS Factory	Governance & collaboration	Project planning & coordination	Supply chain & stakeholders	Quality control	Knowledge management
MAKER (Copenhagen)	Member-driven association, strong autonomy; Formal rules still limited; Reliance on direct communication	Good onboarding and monthly meetings; Strategic planning weak, storage/project duration rules ad hoc	Strong local supplier ties, member enterprises supported; Circularity practices in place	Peer checks and staff oversight; No formal QA, feedback informal	QR linked; training modules; Recurring Member meetups; Limited long-term documentation

TMDC (Barcelona)	User autonomy with project managers for large builds; Few site-wide templates	Ad hoc planning with spreadsheets, Telegram, in-person; Limited formal integration	Co-working model integrates SMEs and schools, short supply chains; Circularity still emerging	Improves parameters through training/experimentation; No formal QA	Peer-to-peer training on advanced tools; Documentation limited
METALAB (Ivano-Frankivsk)	Frequent internal check-ins, agile decisions; Formalisation still developing	Moving toward integrated planning tools; Still partial reliance on manual boards	Regional partnerships, recycled inputs integrated; Broader sourcing still needed for some materials	Feedback sessions and documented fixes; No certification	Mentorship and events support transfer; No formalised repositories
FCHH (Hamburg)	Community model, agile conflict resolution; Volunteer-based, fragile continuity	Nextcloud calendars, Trello and informal exchanges; Ad hoc project adaptation	Distributed networks of labs; Neighborhood participation; Circularity moderate	Machine usage logs and volunteer checks; No formal QA	Regular intro-workshops; Volunteer model hinders sustained curricula
SUPSI (Lugano)	Structured governance through academic programs; Combines autonomy with teaching integration	Planning integrated with curricula; Still fragmented across courses	Regional suppliers and industry ties; Circularity moderate	Informal quality assurance; No certified systems	Training embedded in courses, safety and machine learning formalised; Documentation partial
BUW (Weimar)	Governance embedded in university structures; Informal peer autonomy	Coordination mostly reactive; Weak integration with broader strategy	University partnerships, some local sourcing; Circularity not systematic	Relies on peer oversight; No formal quality assessment framework	Comprehensive wiki for projects, protocols; Strong continuity mechanism
UL (Nancy)	Governance embedded in university structures; Coordination	Scheduling ad hoc, priority to emergencies; Weak	Engages artists, students, associations, SMEs; Strong circular	Recognises need for data-driven QA; Progress still limited	Tutorials in FabManager, videos and GitHub;

	with externals fragmented	integration with strategy	activities (Green FabLab) ; Collaboration w/ external waste partners		Knowledge capturing low
MEKANIKA (Brussels)	Professional production focus, team-led governance ; Community involvement secondary	Structured workflows, industrial orientation; Limited participatory planning	Local suppliers and demonstration projects ; Circularity not systematic	Industrial-style routines, feedback-based checks; No certification	Mentorship and training present; Limited open documentation

5.3.1 Manufacturing structure

Distributed governance

Across the eight factories, decentralised governance is the dominant pattern, balancing flexibility with emerging needs for formalisation. Survey responses confirm that the majority of factories the design and production teams are directly involved in decision-making, while only three indicate systematic integration of project planning with strategic objectives. In practice, most sites allow members or project teams to make operational choices independently, with central coordination reserved for larger or risk-intensive jobs. At MAKER, members manage their own projects and machine access, while the team increasingly formalises storage limits and project durations as activity grows. TMDC similarly privileges user autonomy but appoints a project manager for major builds, combining simple tools such as spreadsheets or Asana with routine face-to-face exchanges. FCHH embodies a community-led model with demand-driven project planning and coordination occurs in real time during open days. By contrast, UL exhibits ad hoc scheduling governed by emergencies and resource windows, with MS Teams supporting internal communication but fragmented exchanges with external partners. METALAB relies on frequent internal check-ins and is gradually replacing manual boards with more integrated planning tools. Overall, governance is flexible and user-driven, which supports responsiveness, but is often fragmented across informal channels, making continuity harder to ensure.

Inter-organisational collaboration

Survey data show that six factories report regular involvement of external partners in projects, including universities, SMEs, artists, and civic organisations. Case narratives illustrate this diversity. TMDC anchors collaboration in a co-working for fabricators model, hosting SMEs and independent makers alongside shared workshops. METALAB builds partnerships with regional firms and leverages recycled inputs, such as Roman concrete and textiles, through industrial collaborations. UL integrates artists, students, associations, and companies, and its Green FabLab initiative connects plastic reuse projects with local waste providers. MAKER maintains daily ties with material suppliers and engages member enterprises through events and surveys. SUPSI actively supports startups to execute small-batch production that is economically unviable for large-scale factories and strategically manages high-volume or specialized requests by redirecting them to a localized network of external manufacturing companies and maintaining a public directory of alternative service providers. FCHH is embedded in a distributed urban network, linking labs, universities, and local firms through projects such as

neighbourhood electronics repair. MEKANIKA demonstrates strong inter-organizational collaboration by sourcing components locally or regionally (e.g. custom steel parts) and through comprehensive training programs and support for their open-source hardware machines. These cases demonstrate how external networks enhance capacity and legitimacy, even if coordination tools are uneven and often fragmented across platforms.

Key findings - Manufacturing structure

Factories show high flexibility in governance, with most enabling distributed decision-making at team level. This supports agility but often relies on informal coordination, making planning fragmented and handovers less reliable. External collaboration is a shared strength, as six factories actively involve universities, SMEs, artists, and civic partners in projects, creating dense local and regional networks. The balance of autonomy and collaboration underpins responsiveness, but traceability and consistency remain weaker.

5.3.2 Project planning and coordination

Integration

Survey results highlight that only a minority of factories integrate project planning with broader strategic objectives. Three of eight sites report systematic alignment between operational tasks and longer-term priorities, while most manage projects in a more reactive or case-by-case manner. The case material illustrates this divergence. At UL, scheduling is largely ad hoc, with priority given to urgent requests and available time windows rather than a structured calendar. MAKER employs OfficeRnD to manage bookings and Slack for coordination, but integration with longer-term planning is limited to broad rules such as storage limits and project durations. TMDC uses spreadsheets or Asana for major projects and appoints project managers where necessary, yet site-wide templates and protocols remain scarce. FCHH relies on open lab dynamics, where planning emerges through collective adjustment during events. METALAB is transitioning from manual boards to more integrated digital planning tools, indicating a move toward more structured integration. Overall, project integration remains weakly formalised, with most sites relying on pragmatic short-term coordination.

Information sharing

Information sharing is more developed than integration, though it remains uneven. Survey responses show that all factories use digital platforms to share data and updates, with 5 of 8 describing information as “easily searchable.” In practice, repositories coexist with informal channels. MAKER provides a welcome pack, onboarding handbook, QR posters with online guides, and newsletters, complemented by Slack and monthly meetings. UL uses MS Teams for internal files, but collaborations with external communities often happen on Slack, WhatsApp, or Discord, leading to silos. TMDC leans heavily on in-person exchanges, complemented by a Telegram group for questions and offers, while public updates are disseminated via Instagram. FCHH maintains shared calendars and folders on Nextcloud, but informal discussions during open days remain central. The survey that all factories report structured data sharing, most also acknowledge reliance on informal exchanges. Thus, information is widely shared but not always consolidated.

Process adaptation and flexibility

Survey data confirm that flexibility in processes is a strong trait: six factories rate their adaptability to project changes at the upper end of the scale, indicating moderate to high readiness for

reconfiguration. Case evidence reinforces this. TMDC's co-working model allows SMEs and independent makers to scale their activity by renting additional units as needed. MAKER adjusts quickly by rearranging spaces and reassigning machines, although this flexibility sometimes clashes with storage limits and calendar conflicts. UL adapts to emergencies by reallocating slots on short notice, while FCHH responds directly to community demand during open labs. METALAB organises frequent internal check-ins, enabling fast decision-making and resource shifts. SUPSI integrates adaptability into teaching projects, adjusting machine allocations and staff support as student cohorts change. Across the cohort, flexibility is a common strength, compensating for the absence of formal integration.

Key findings - Project planning and coordination

Factories show weak formal integration between day-to-day operations and long-term planning, with only three of eight reporting systematic alignment. However, information sharing is well established, with all sites using digital tools and most offering searchable data, though silos remain due to parallel informal channels. Flexibility is the strongest feature, with six factories reporting high adaptability in reallocating resources and adjusting workflows. Together, this profile shows project coordination that is agile and responsive, but fragmented and weakly formalised.

5.3.3 Supply chain management

Local supply chains

Survey results indicate that most factories maintain relatively short supply chains, though with varying degrees of localisation. Four of eight report sourcing the majority of materials within their city or region, while others rely more heavily on continental suppliers for specialised inputs. TMDC prioritises city-based suppliers and short lead times to serve SMEs and independent makers in Barcelona. MAKER maintains daily links with local material suppliers and supports member enterprises through small-batch supply. METALAB integrates local recycled inputs such as Roman concrete and textiles into its workflows. UL works with nearby waste providers to fuel its Green FabLab activities. These practices confirm that local supply integration is present but not yet universal, with reliance on broader networks still common for specialised or industrial-grade inputs.

Stakeholder integration

Stakeholder involvement is a shared strength across the network. Survey results show that six factories report regular participation of external stakeholders (including universities, SMEs, artists, and community groups) in projects. Case material adds depth: TMDC anchors its model in co-working for fabricators, directly integrating SMEs and professionals into daily operations. UL builds multi-actor collaborations with artists, associations, and companies, combining academic and community engagement. FCHH fosters co-design and co-production through its distributed network of labs, universities, and firms, frequently involving neighbourhood participants in projects such as community electronics. MAKER collects feedback through surveys and hosts member-driven events and festivals, reinforcing a participatory model. These practices demonstrate that stakeholder integration is a consistent asset across cases, enhancing innovation and legitimacy.

Circularity

Survey data show that circular practices are moderately present: five factories report some form of material reuse or recycling, while structured circularity strategies are less common. Table 9 presents a

matrix representation of circular practice implementation across the LAUDS case settings, with accompanying marginal distributions indicating the relative prevalence of each practice.

Table 9: Matrix of implemented circular practices across LAUDS Factories

In-house waste recycling	✓	✓	✓					
Reducing virgin material use	✓	✓			✓			
Reducing energy consumption	✓			✓	✓			
Sharing waste between businesses	✓	✓	✓				✓	
Refurbishing older products	✓	✓	✓	✓				
Reducing non-recyclable materials	✓				✓	✓	✓	
Manufacturing waste sorting	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		
Using locally sourced materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
Reducing need for material	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓
Repurposing used components	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Reducing material waste	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
	UL, Nancy	MAKER, Copenhagen	TMDC, Barcelona	MEKANIKA, Brussels	FCHH, Hamburg	METALAB, nano-Frankfurt	SUPSI, Lugano	BUW, Weimar

Case examples illustrate early but concrete steps. METALAB partners with regional firms to incorporate recycled textiles and building materials. UL’s Green FabLab develops plastic reuse workflows and collaborates with new waste material providers. TMDC shares stock across tenants and implemented the reuse of wood chips, while FCHH implements fair electronics projects that prioritise repair and repurposing. MAKER supports reuse through member initiatives and small-scale plastic recycling activities. Although systematic frameworks are rare, circular practices are emerging across sites, anchored in local partnerships and experimental pilots.

Analysis of circularity practices across the eight LAUDS case-settings reveals significant variation in implementation rates (overall: 56%). Material waste reduction demonstrates highest adoption (87.5%), followed by component repurposing (75%) and material need reduction (62.5%). University Lorraine Nancy exhibits comprehensive implementation (100%), while MAKER Copenhagen (82%) and TMDC Barcelona (73%) show strong commitment. Critical implementation gaps exist in energy consumption optimization, virgin material substitution, and in-house waste recycling (each 37.5%), indicating substantial potential for inter-organizational knowledge transfer and capacity building in these domains.

Key findings - Supply chain management
 Factories show moderate readiness in local supply, with half sourcing primarily from city or regional networks and others relying on wider continental inputs. Stakeholder integration is a clear strength, as six factories actively involve universities, SMEs, artists, and community groups in co-design and production. Circularity is present but uneven, with most sites reporting some reuse or recycling practices, though systematic frameworks are still lacking. Together, supply chain management

demonstrates strong community anchoring and collaborative networks, while the integration of circular economy principles remains at an early stage.

5.3.4 Quality control and process improvement

Quality measurement systems

Survey results confirm that formal quality systems are largely absent across the factories. Only two of eight report having any structured quality assurance protocols, and none indicate possession of certified systems (such as ISO). Instead, quality management is mostly handled through informal checks, feedback loops, or peer review. The survey also shows that six factories rely primarily on peer assessment during project execution, while five collect external feedback from clients or partners.

The case material illustrates this reliance on informal systems. TMDC improves machine parameters through direct experimentation during training and production runs, but no standardised quality assurance framework has been implemented. METALAB conducts structured feedback sessions and documents issues and fixes, which helps to consolidate lessons but does not amount to a certified process. FCHH uses machine usage logs to trace responsibility and resolve problems, complemented by volunteer checks on key equipment. UL recognises the need for more formal data-driven quality monitoring and is working toward expanding FabManager for this purpose. MAKER and SUPSI use user induction and staff oversight as proxies for quality control rather than codified systems.

Across the network, quality control is thus embedded in social and procedural practices rather than formal certification. This approach provides flexibility and supports peer learning but creates fragility when handling external client work or scaling to small-series production.

Key findings - Quality control and process improvement

Factories currently rely on informal and social mechanisms for quality control. Only two of eight report structured protocols, and none use certified systems. Most sites depend on peer review (6/8) and external feedback (5/8) to monitor outcomes, supported by ad hoc troubleshooting or staff oversight. Case examples confirm that incremental improvements occur through feedback sessions, experimentation, or volunteer checks, but data-driven monitoring and certification are absent. Readiness in this domain is therefore low to moderate, providing agility and learning opportunities but lacking the consistency required for formalised client-facing production.

5.3.5 Knowledge management

Knowledge transfer

Survey results show that knowledge transfer practices are present but uneven across the factories. Six of eight sites report providing some form of structured onboarding or training for new users, while four maintain documentation such as wikis, handbooks, or video tutorials. Peer-to-peer learning remains the dominant mechanism, reported by all sites as central to everyday work. Case evidence highlights these contrasts. BUW has one of the most comprehensive systems, maintaining a wiki that archives projects, code, and protocols, an effective tool for intergenerational transfer in a university setting. MAKER integrates onboarding into OfficeRnD and Slack, with welcome packs, chip keys, QR-linked machine instructions, and regular monthly meetings reinforcing collective knowledge. UL is experimenting with FabManager tutorials, short instructional videos, and GitHub repositories, though

capturing tacit craft knowledge remains a challenge. SUPSI links training to academic curricula, ensuring that machine use and safety are embedded in student learning. FCHH provides regular introductions and workshops, but its volunteer-driven model makes continuity more fragile. METALAB invests in mentorship, networking events, and structured feedback sessions to consolidate learning, while TMDC trains new users on advanced equipment, though knowledge is still mainly exchanged through informal conversations on the shop floor. Overall, the factories show strong cultures of peer learning and mentoring, complemented by emerging documentation systems. Formalisation varies significantly, some sites maintain extensive wikis or repositories, while others rely almost entirely on in-person transfer.

Key findings - Knowledge management

Factories show broad but uneven readiness in knowledge transfer. Six of eight provide structured onboarding, and four maintain wikis or tutorials. Peer-to-peer learning is universal and inclusive, but formal documentation and long-term knowledge capture remain inconsistent.

5.3.6 Recommendations – Organisational infrastructure

The organisational layer excels in flexibility, collaboration, and openness, but lacks formalisation, quality assurance, and systematic knowledge capture. User needs push strongly for business support, mentorship, and visibility opportunities.

Table 10: Recommendation matrix for organisational infrastructure

Start Doing	Keep Doing
Project planning templates (Capacity), Basic quality assurance protocols (Capacity), Systematic documentation (Capacity), Entrepreneurial support services (User), Structured onboarding and residencies (User)	Decentralised participatory governance (Capacity), Local/regional collaborations (Capacity), Peer-to-peer mentoring and social learning (User), Shared hubs for affordable access (User)
Watch	Leverage
Over-reliance on informal coordination (Capacity), Weak quality assurance limiting scaling (Capacity), Knowledge loss from undocumented expertise (Capacity), Institutional/commercial dominance (User)	Knowledge transfer systems (Capacity), Formalised co-design and co-production (Capacity), Expanded visibility & showcasing (User), Stronger urban & cultural partnerships (User), Distributed communities of practice (User)

The integrated recommendations therefore emphasise starting with lightweight formalisation (planning, QA, documentation) while scaling existing collaboration and learning practices and ensuring that support services remain inclusive and accessible.

6. Discussion

In the eight LAUDS Factories, our mixed-methods analysis (survey and interviews) highlights a common basis of accessibility, openness, and operational adaptability, reinforced by strong local networks of SMEs, artists, civic actors, and universities. These characteristics underpin the agility needed for prototyping and small-batch production and illustrate the contribution of urban manufacturing to embedding production within local ecosystems. This also resonates with the Fab City vision of infrastructures that are “locally productive and globally connected,” grounded in peer learning and community anchoring (Fab City Global Initiative, 2016).

At the same time, structural weaknesses are found in all cases, like persistent space saturation, bottlenecks on high-demand machines, fragmented material handling, and limited formalisation of preventive maintenance, quality assurance, and documented procedures. Digital capabilities are rich in tools but often inefficiently integrated; automation and monitoring are in their early stages; and energy monitoring remains at the ‘future projects’ stage. These findings reflect broader challenges documented in the literature, where most of makerspaces and collaborative production spaces remain focused on experimentation, learning, and design rather than full production (Hennelly et al., 2019; Freeman et al., 2017). However, our hypothesis suggests that not all spaces need to become production-intensive. Their value lies in leveraging specific strengths to empower local actors (e.g., artists, creatives, entrepreneurs) who often lack production infrastructure

The findings indicate that scaling up is not simply a question of size or equipment and illustrate distinct strategic orientations shaping their readiness. Larger factories such as TMDC face coordination challenges despite extensive space and tools, while smaller sites like BUW and UL show that governance design and scheduling discipline can buffer against constraints. In this sense, resilience is best understood as scale-up capacity aligned to mission. Production-oriented hubs such as TMDC or MEKANIKA need to address bottlenecks in space, machines, and automation to move toward semi-industrial performance. Academic labs like SUPSI or BUW need to strengthen digital integration and planning to reconcile teaching schedules with external production demands. Community-driven spaces like FCHH and METALAB require light but consistent maintenance and quality assurance routines to reduce dependence on individual volunteers. Living-lab demonstrators such as LSCLL (UL), with strong partnerships but informal production management, must stabilise workflows to make their collaborative potential scalable.

From this perspective, the discussion of readiness is not about convergence toward a single industrial model but about addressing the specific bottlenecks within each readiness layer that currently prevent factories from scaling in line with their missions. These diverse approaches highlight the need for development strategies that go beyond infrastructure metrics and consider the intended function and trajectory of each type of space. Future research should examine how such differentiated models contribute to sustainable urban manufacturing by supporting various stages of production and broadening access to local capabilities.

7. Conclusion

The objective of this work was to analyse the manufacturing capacity of LAUDS infrastructures to support creatives, artists, and entrepreneurs in experimenting, developing, and scaling their projects. To do so, we introduced and applied a three-layer conceptual framework (physical, digital, and organisational) which represents a new contribution to the literature. This framework allowed us to empirically analyse eight case studies and to identify how readiness in each layer enables or constrains the scaling of ideas from prototyping into more consistent and reliable forms of production.

The results show that the LAUDS Factories are already inclusive, accessible, and adaptable, acting as critical infrastructures for innovation and collaboration. Yet their ability to scale up in urban, local and sustainable manufacturing activities is constrained by recurring bottlenecks in space saturation, limited machine capabilities and weak energy efficiency practices in the physical layer; fragmented workflows and minimal monitoring in the digital layer; and reactive planning, informal quality assurance, and uneven documentation in the organisational layer. These limitations mean that the factories are resilient in everyday prototyping and small-batch production, their capacity under growth and stress remains fragile. At the same time, the cases illustrate diverse scale-up pathways (production hubs, academic labs, community spaces, and living labs) each requiring differentiated forms of support.

Limitations of the study

The deliverable faces certain limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample includes only eight factories. Although chosen for their diversity, this sample cannot capture the full heterogeneity of urban factories across Europe, particularly in different regional or industrial contexts. Second, the methodology relied partly on self-reported data through surveys and interviews, which carries risks of bias, selective emphasis, or over-optimism. More observational and performance-based data would increase robustness. Third, the temporal scope was limited. Readiness is dynamic and influenced by evolving demand, funding cycles, and crises. Cross-sectional evidence cannot capture these longitudinal dynamics. Finally, the focus of analysis was on technical infrastructure readiness, meaning less attention was given to complementary aspects such as financial sustainability, user impact, or in-depth environmental performance.

Future research and next steps

Building on this foundation, four priorities emerge:

1. **Longitudinal monitoring of infrastructures:** Future research should track readiness over extended periods to capture how infrastructures adapt, mature, or respond to shocks. This would make it possible to distinguish temporary bottlenecks from structural barriers and assess the lasting effects of interventions.
2. **Application of the three-layer framework to a larger European sample:** The framework should be applied systematically across a broader and more representative set of factories. This will test its robustness, reveal regional variations, and provide an evidence base to inform policy and funding at the European level.
3. **Development of a self-assessment maturity tool:** Translating the framework into a practical self-assessment tool would empower LAUDS Factory managers and operators to evaluate their technical readiness profiles, identify bottlenecks, and track progress autonomously.

Aggregated self-assessments could also provide policymakers with a bottom-up view of readiness across Europe.

4. **Further exploration of scale-up strategies:** More work is needed to understand how different types of urban factories can progress from prototyping toward more consistent and repeatable production. Comparative research should examine which organisational practices, governance approaches, and contextual conditions enable successful scale-up while preserving inclusiveness and openness.

References

- M. Grubbauer, A. Manganelli, and L. Volont, Eds., *Conflicts in Urban Future-Making: Governance, Institutions, and Transformative Change*, 1st ed. Bielefeld, Germany: transcript Verlag, 2024. doi: 10.14361/9783839474679.
- J. C. Markert, D. Saubke, P. Krenz, and J. P. Wulfsberg, "Quality Management in a Production Network of Local MSEs from the Manufacturing Sector - A Literature Review," in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*, Bangkok, Thailand: IEEE, Dec. 2024, pp. 1204–1208. doi: 10.1109/IEEM62345.2024.10857253.
- M. S. Amjad and N. Diaz-Elsayed, "Smart and sustainable urban manufacturing for a circular economy," *Environ Dev Sustain*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 31789–31815, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s10668-024-04671-w.
- A. S. Abubakar, "Adopting Digital Technology to Drive Resource Efficiency in Manufacturing," May 2024, doi: 10.17863/CAM.108569.
- S. M. M. Sajadieh and S. D. Noh, "Towards Sustainable Manufacturing: A Maturity Assessment for Urban Smart Factory," *Int. J. of Precis. Eng. and Manuf.-Green Tech.*, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s40684-023-00554-z.
- T. Sakao, N. Bocken, N. Nasr, and Y. Umeda, "Implementing circular economy activities in manufacturing for environmental sustainability," *CIRP Annals*, vol. 73, no. 2, pp. 457–481, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.cirp.2024.06.002.
- M. Savastano, F. Bellini, and F. D'Ascenzo, "FabLab and Digital Manufacturing: Innovative Tools for Social Innovation and Value Co-creation," in *Smart Technologies for Organizations*, C. Dal Zotto, A. Omidj, and G. Aoun, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 193–214. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-24775-0_12.
- M. Omer, M. Kaiser, M. Moritz, S. Buxbaum-Conradi, T. Redlich, and J. P. Wulfsberg, "Democratizing Manufacturing – Evaluating the Potential of Open Source Machine Tools as Drivers of Sustainable Industrial Development in Resource Constrained Contexts," pp. 256–266, 2022, doi: 10.15488/12154.
- L. Hildebrandt, T. Redlich, and J. P. Wulfsberg, "Production Planning And Control In Distributed And Networked Open Production Sites – An Integrative Literature Review," 2021, doi: 10.15488/11292.
- Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (European Commission) et al., *The impact of open source software and hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy: final study report*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2021. Accessed: Jul. 07, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/430161>
- C. Herrmann, M. Juraschek, P. Burggräf, and S. Kara, "Urban production: State of the art and future trends for urban factories," *CIRP Annals*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 764–787, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cirp.2020.05.003.
- S. Abdoli, M. Juraschek, S. Thiede, S. Kara, and C. Herrmann, "An Investigation into Holistic Planning of Urban Factories," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 80, pp. 649–654, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2019.01.100.
- A. Vetter, "The Matrix of Convivial Technology – Assessing technologies for degrowth," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 197, pp. 1778–1786, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.02.195.
- M. Juraschek, B. Vossen, H. Hoffschroer, C. Reicher, and C. Herrmann, "Urbane Produktion: Ökonomie als Analogie für eine nachhaltige Wertschöpfung in Städten," in *Interdisziplinäre Perspektiven zur Zukunft der Wertschöpfung*, T. Redlich, M. Moritz, and J. P. Wulfsberg, Eds., Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2018, pp. 195–207. doi: 10.1007/978-3-658-20265-1_15.

A. Barni, D. Corti, P. Pedrazzoli, D. Rovere, and G. Lucisano, "Mini-factories for Close-to-customer Manufacturing of Customized Furniture: From Concept to Real Demo," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 11, pp. 854–862, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2017.07.188.

M. Savastano, F. Bellini, F. D'Ascenzo, and E. Scornavacca, "FabLabs as Platforms for Digital Fabrication Services: A Literature Analysis," in *Exploring Services Science*, S. Za, M. Drăgoicea, and M. Cavallari, Eds., in *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 24–37. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-56925-3_3.

T. Redlich, M. Moritz, S. Buxbaum-Conradi, P. Krenz, S. Heubischl, and S.-V. Basmer-Birkenfeld, "OpenLabs - Collaborative Industrialization with Distributed and Open Source Microfactories," *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 794, pp. 470–477, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.794.470.

P. Krenz, S.-V. Basmer-Birkenfeld, S. Buxbaum-Conradi, T. Redlich, and J. Wulfsberg, "Knowledge Management in Value Creation Networks: Establishing a New Business Model through the Role of a Knowledge-Intermediary," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 16, pp. 38–43, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2014.01.006.

J. Wulfsberg, T. Redlich, and F.-L. Bruhns, "Open production: Scientific foundation for co-creative product realization," *Production Engineering*, vol. 5, pp. 127–139, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1007/s11740-010-0286-6.

Appendix

Appendix 1. Example of individual report – Maker V10 (Copenhagen, Denmark)

Figure 8: Screenshots from website of MAKER

MAKER (Copenhagen, Denmark) is a hybrid workshop and creative hub integrating digital tools (CNC, laser cutters, 3D printers) with traditional craftsmanship. Designed for accessibility, they support small-batch production, material innovation, and custom work, aiming to foster opportunities for entrepreneurship.

What expertise you can offer?

"We offer a variety of options tailored to meet the needs of a diverse range of individuals, from creative freelancers and startups to hobbyists and established companies.

With digital production technologies and traditional craftsmanship, V-10 is a meeting place for people with different backgrounds and interests. Our ever evolving facilities is made for entrepreneurs and companies who are curious and open to exploring new opportunities and pushing the boundaries of urban and local production in a globalised world.

*Join the community at V-10, where we focus on product development, business, design and tech. Here, you will have access to our co-working area, all machines and tools, including 3D printers, lasers, CNC milling machines, power tools, and more. Additionally, we offer common materials such as plywood, MDF, cardboard, acrylic, and more."*⁶

⁶ Source : <https://lauds.eu/stories/interview-to-malte-hertz-jansen-maker-v10>

Physical infrastructure readiness

Figure 9: Spacelayout of MAKER

Space

Spatial adaptability and versatility: MAKER's approach aims to keep the space as dynamic as possible. Machines are only purchased when there is a clear need for them, or when there is potential for new business areas or member groups. This approach is reflected in the adaptability of the workshop areas. For instance, the metal workshop was reduced in size due to low usage, while the wood workshop and assembly area were significantly expanded to meet demand.

"Our makerspace is organized into dedicated workshops for different types of projects, including woodworking, electronics, 3D printing, ceramics, and metalworking. This setup ensures a safer and more efficient workflow while allowing specialized equipment to be used in the appropriate environment."

The facility includes various specialised areas, including a CNC workshop, a wood workshop, an assembly area, a metal workshop, a digital and electronics manufacturing area, a paint room, a bio lab, a co-working area, and meeting rooms. There is also a flexible event room measuring 120 square feet that can be used as a photo studio and for large-format projects. The total area is 1,000 square metres. MAKER is planning to move to a new location that is twice the size, which will offer more capacity for different user groups.

Space accessibility: The workshop is open 24/7. Members can purchase access. Accessibility is a core principle of MAKER. Instead of strict online booking systems for most machines and workstations, the concept emphasises personal interactions and self-organisation in order to promote spontaneous use and collaboration. Exception is the the Full Sheet CNC which is equipped with a machine access system, mainly due to safety reason

Integration into the urban space: MAKER is located at Vasbygade 10, 2450 Copenhagen SV, in close proximity to densely populated areas. The planned move to a new warehouse in the city centre ('Lab 17') further emphasises this urban integration. However, gentrification in Copenhagen brings high rents and other challenges. As MAKER grows, regulatory requirements regarding noise, dust emissions and safety are becoming an increasingly important issue. MAKER promotes 'local production' and waste separation through green outdoor containers and white buckets. Members are responsible for disposing of large or hazardous waste themselves. MAKER's current location is temporary and they are actively searching for new sites, including a large warehouse in the city centre. This suggests that they are making use of, or converting, existing urban buildings.

Machines & equipment

Multifunctionality/versatility: The workshop supports both prototype development and production. Examples of small-batch production include furniture, material innovations, and paper products made from recycled paper (Studio Circolar), as well as customised kitchens, small sensors and restored knives up to real-size train models.

Figure 10: Distribution of existent equipment processes at MAKER V-10

The range of available machines, including table saws, planers/thicknessers, crosscut saws, band saws, laser cutters, 3D printers and CNC machines including the Shapeoko XXL and Full Sheet CNC with Automatic Tool Changer, offer a high degree of versatility for a variety of manufacturing processes.

Machine accessibility: Some machines require licences and introductory courses. Mandatory courses are required for metal workshops, 3D printers, laser cutters and CNC machines. MAKER prefers user-friendly machines with which members are already familiar, often from their education or professional experience. To ensure accessibility, comprehensive instructions (including tutorials and specifications) are provided via OfficeRnD and supplemented by physical posters with QR codes. MAKER also provides guidance on how to adjust the machines themselves (e.g. changing blades or nozzles on 3D printers).

Machine openness: MAKER can carry out most repairs in-house and has spare parts available to minimise downtime. The Prusa 3D printers are partly based on an open-source structure. A challenge with open-source hardware is that users are often unfamiliar with it and prefer to use what they

already know. Nevertheless, MAKER recommends open-source software alternatives, such as Inkscape for laser cutters and Blender for 3D printing, because they are of a high quality and are accessible.

Operations

Material handling: Members can store materials for ongoing projects free of charge for up to two weeks. Storing materials for longer than this period or storing 'special sizes' is subject to a fee. Special shelves and pallets are available for project storage, as well as personal storage areas which can be rented. MAKER encourages members to order materials as and when needed, rather than stockpiling them. A major bottleneck is the limited workspace, especially when several members are working on large projects simultaneously, which restricts capacity for further projects. MAKER is developing a more structured management system for projects and storage.

Maintenance and internal capacity for reliability: According to MAKER, the machines rarely break down. Although 3D printers can malfunction due to different uses or changes in filament type, the availability of spare parts ensures quick recovery. Power tools are subject to wear and tear due to intensive use. Maintenance costs increase with member activity (e.g. cleaning mirrors and lenses on laser cutters and replacing vacuum bags).

LAUDS Factory	weekly servicing	monthly servicing	biannual servicing	annual servicing	serviced as needed
MAKER (Copenhagen)	Dust collection systems (filter cleaning and emptying); Laser cutters (service, mirror, lens cleaning, alignment and focus); Sliding table saw; Thicknesser and planer	3D printers; CNC mills	Filter change and cleaning of external fume extraction connected to laser cutters	N/A	All machines and tools are serviced when needed. We rarely have downtime on our machines or tools.

Regular service and maintenance cycles (monthly, weekly, quarterly or annual) contribute to high reliability. External technicians are only occasionally needed for larger woodworking machines or laser cutters, as most tasks can be performed internally. Lab manager Asger Nørregård Rasmussen is responsible for coordinating courses and resolving workshop issues.

Equipment reconfiguration: Workshops are kept 'as dynamic as possible' and adapted to usage requirements. For example, the metal workshop is scaled down in favour of the wood workshop and assembly area. The machines themselves offer built-in flexibility, for example, CNC machines have automatic tool changers, saws have interchangeable blades and 3D printers have different nozzles. According to MAKER, the degree of automation is 'mostly manual with some automation'. The full-sheet CNC machine has an automatic tool changer, while 3D printers and laser cutters are 'partially automated'. However, material handling remains manual. MAKER deliberately refrains from further automation, such as the use of robots, due to budget and space constraints, and to avoid compromising accessibility by requiring technical specialists.

Material Management: Members can either bring their own materials or have them delivered. MAKER collaborates with selected suppliers of primary materials, such as plywood and fibreboard. Daily delivery from www.krydsfiner.dk is available.

Adaptation and flexibility (Changeoverability): MAKER specialises in small-batch production, often on demand, with typical batch sizes ranging from one to ten units. The product range is extensive and includes furniture, artistic objects and specialised components. The workshop is run informally to encourage self-organisation and flexibility among its members. MAKER is 'as flexible as possible' when it comes to handling urgent projects and rarely turns down requests. Members are expected to coordinate with each other. However, the flexibility of the facility is limited by its size and fixed infrastructure (e.g. electric supply). Continuous adjustments are made on an ad hoc basis to optimise storage space, such as weekly reminders for project notes.

Energy Efficiency

Renewable energy sources: MAKER does not currently use its own renewable energy sources, such as solar panels, because it does not own the building and is only located there temporarily. The heating system is based on district heating, which is considered environmentally friendly in Denmark and does not use gas. A long-term goal is to become energy self-sufficient.

Energy efficiency: To date, no specific energy efficiency measures have been implemented, such as tracking machine consumption for optimisation purposes. However, MAKER would like to collect machine usage data, such as the running times of laser cutters and the filament consumption of 3D printers, in order to optimise maintenance schedules and plan for spare parts requirements more effectively. A local AI tool developed by one of MAKER members is intended to be more energy efficient in operation compared to global AI infrastructures, seeing self-hosted AI equipment as possible additional equipment.

Digital infrastructure readiness

Digital tools

Integration: MAKER uses OfficeRnD for managing members, booking rooms and providing access to training materials. Slack is used for daily internal communication and the exchange of information. Specific machines, such as the Full Sheet CNC, are booked and accessed via Fabman Access Management System. Computer-aided Design (CAD) and manufacturing (CAM) software such as Prusa Slicer (for 3D printers), Lightburn (lasercutters) and Fusion 360 (for CNC-milling) are in use. Different tools are used for different functions to achieve integration.

Automation: According to MAKER, the degree of automation is 'mostly manual with some automation'. The full-sheet CNC machine has an automatic tool changer, while 3D printers and laser cutters are 'partially automated'. However, material handling remains manual. MAKER deliberately refrains from further automation, such as the use of robots, due to budget and space constraints, and to avoid compromising accessibility by requiring technical specialists.

Accessibility: Fusion 360 was chosen as the basic software for CNC courses due to its affordability and accessibility (with a free non-commercial licence and affordable professional licence). MAKER also

recommends free, open-source alternatives such as Inkscape and Blender to make usage of tools as 'democratic as possible'.

Openness: Prusa's 3D printers and the main management system for bookings, Fabman, are both based on open-source structures. MAKER actively promotes open-source software, including Inkscape and Blender. A local AI tool, which was developed by a community member and trained using community data, promotes a local, open and community-oriented approach for the use of AI.

Adaptability and flexibility: There are no significant challenges in terms of file compatibility or interoperability between the various tools, since the "languages of digital manufacturing are universal". The fact that members use different design software like Blender, Grasshopper, SolidWorks or Rhino, suggests that the digital workbench is flexible enough to support different choices, as long as the output is compatible.

Data management

Data sharing: Internal communication and information dissemination takes place daily via Slack and OfficeRnD. Members are encouraged to introduce themselves on Slack to strengthen the sense of community. Monthly member meetings provide a secure internal space for discussing projects, needs and improvements where staff also share insights from MAKER projects.

Storage and file system: OfficeRnD serves as a digital repository for member data, bookings, and 'how-to' guides. While there is no structured file system for members' project data, such as CAD/CAM files, the compatibility of the tools used suggests that different file types can be handled. Users manufacturing data remains mainly in their toolchain and structure. Internally Google Drive supports the exchange of files.

Data monitoring

Process tracking: Although MAKER can retrieve usage data from machines such as 3D printers (e.g. filament consumption) and laser cutters (e.g. running time) through machine logbooks file, this data is difficult to extract and use effectively. There is a desire to integrate this data into maintenance plans in order to enable predictive maintenance and improve the planning of spare parts requirements. MAKER also wants to collect usage data on the facility (e.g. occupancy times) to obtain political acceptance and financial support. Another challenge is collecting data on members' data from workshop use, as this information is private so compliance with data protection regulations must be considered.

Network connectivity: The building relies on unstable 5G, which is a major problem as it results in a lack of stable internet connection. This significantly impairs the digital infrastructure, potentially limiting the interoperability and reliability of digital workflows.

Organizational infrastructure readiness

Manufacturing structure

Decentralised governance, decentralisation and peer production: Members act largely autonomously in their manufacturing activities. MAKER acts as an intermediary for external production requests, forwarding them to the members. Members manage their own machine and space usage, with the exception of full sheet CNC bookings. This informal structure is favoured to encourage personal interaction and self-organisation. MAKER provides access to tools and facilities, as well as courses and a supportive experienced community.

Inter-organisational collaboration: Internally, MAKER is a non-profit association that encourages networking and knowledge sharing among its members. Externally, it collaborates with material suppliers and participates in EU-funded projects.

"Maker V-10 facilitates and handle external client requests incoming our info mail. We either communicate this as an open offer to our members via internal communication channels and/or we set up a team of members and staff to realise the client request. However, our members handle their own clients."

Members collaborate with external partners on their individual level. Its members' work is disseminated via social media and the website.

Project planning and coordination

Integration: There is no long-term strategic planning for individual member projects; members manage their own project schedules. However, MAKER is developing a more formal management system for internal and external projects, particularly with regard to storage and project duration, as the informal system is reaching its limits due to an increasing number of professional members and continuous production.

Information sharing: OfficeRnD and Slack are used for daily communication and the provision of information. New members receive welcome emails and a chip key, as well as an introduction to the digital platforms and the member handbook. All courses and introductory materials are available online via OfficeRnD. MAKER regularly provides information about activities and opportunities and sends out a monthly newsletter. QR codes on physical posters link to comprehensive online instructions.

Process adaptation and flexibility: For short-term or urgent projects, "continuous negotiation and adaptation" is employed. MAKER strives to be as flexible as possible and rarely turns down urgent requests. Members are expected to coordinate urgent requests themselves. MAKER responds to problems as they arise, working together as a team to develop solutions and make minor adjustments.

Supply-Chain Management

Local supply chain: MAKER values local production. Members often produce items on demand. Examples include "Quirky Moose", which manufactures furniture for end customers on demand, and "Studio Circolar", which uses wastepaper from Copenhagen museums for its products.

"Materials can be ordered through Maker. We have established and/or bought access to various material platforms and suppliers - including both virgin materials and "new waste" materials. We provide the service of buying materials from our in-house material shop (currently materials for laser cutting and 3D print, but will be expanded to more materials in a near future)."

There is a daily delivery of plywood, and the company collaborates with other material suppliers who are likely to be based locally or regionally.

Stakeholders' integration: MAKER is a non-profit association that supports physical entrepreneurs. Members can participate in festivals, be hired for production tasks, take part in exhibitions, use the workshop facilities, assist with event organisation and contribute to grant applications.

"In Maker V-10 the designers are most often also the manufacturer. Meetings are organised to plan a design and manufacturing process. "

The community is strongly promoted, and emphasis is placed on members getting to know each other and communicating. Half-yearly member surveys are used to collect feedback and suggestions.

Circular economy: MAKER member 'Studio Circolar' experiments with wastepaper and biofiber materials.

"Educating, inspiring or communicating about design principles that reduce the use of virgin materials to members and broader community. We do this as part of workshops, events and projects (internal and open to the public). Maker has bought access to a local platform for "new waste materials", The UpCycl, from where our members can buy waste materials from various industries."

Members are encouraged to dispose of materials in separate containers and are responsible for disposing of large or hazardous waste themselves. A plastic recycling program was introduced in the summer.

Quality control and process improvement

Quality measurement system: There is no explicit mention of a formal quality measurement system or certification for manufacturing processes.

"Peer review happens on both formal and informal ways. In the everyday work life in Maker V-10 staff and members are continuously reviewing and giving feedback on projects or products. As part of residency programs peer review and sharing sessions are applied for feedback, often also including external specialists."

The focus is on accessibility and supporting members with their diverse projects. Members/entrepreneurs are responsible for the quality of the end product. Feedback is collected via biannual surveys. Machine maintenance cycles focus on equipment reliability.

Knowledge management

Knowledge management: MAKER offers introductory courses on various machines, including CNC, laser cutters and 3D printers, as well as general workshop safety. Training materials are available online at OfficeRnD. Monthly meetings enable members to share projects, experiences and knowledge. Staff also share insights from projects. One member is currently developing a local AI tool based on the community's specific knowledge of aesthetics and production methods, which is a form of knowledge management.

Appendix 2.a Survey questionnaire - Form

General information

Note 1: Questions that are targeted at "you" refer to staff and users of the space.

Note 2: throughout Section 1, there are several questions that will require you to list your machines or tools according to the answer you selected. We recommend that you create a short list of some of the main machines used for manufacturing products in your space beforehand (don't include things like hand tools or jigs). This is to make it easier and faster for you to fill out the questions.

*** Which case setting are you?**

- UL: University Lorraine, Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab
- MAK: Maker, Copenhagen
- FCHH: Fab City Hamburg
- TMDC: Taller para la Materialización y Desarrollo de Conceptos, Barcelona
- SUPSI: FabLab SUPSI, Lugano
- BUW: Bauhaus University Weimar, Berlin
- MEK: Mekanika, Brussels
- METALAB, Ivano-Frankivsk

*** Who is present to answer this survey? (Select all that apply)**

- Manager (e.g. lab manager, innovation manager)
- Technician (e.g. equipment operator, maintainer, etc.)
- Professional User (e.g. craftsman, engineer, designer, artist, etc.)
- Other (please specify)

Other (please specify)

*** What is the main activity of your site/organization?**

*** How long has your site/organization been in operation?**

SECTION 1: PHYSICAL CAPABILITIES

1.1 General overview

This section aims to understand the general setup and focus of the space.

• **1. What are the primary products, services or prototypes that you offer?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Custom prototypes (e.g. for industries)
- Small-batch products
- Art installations
- Community projects (non-profit projects created with and intended for local people and/or associations, DIY projects)
- Other *(please specify)*

• Other *(please specify)*

• **2. How would you describe the scale of your operations?** *(Select one)*

- Small (individual projects and prototypes)
- Medium (small batch or community-focused production)
- Large (consistent output or collaboration with multiple clients)

Comment

• **3. How many people work constantly in your space (e.g. employees, users with permanent presence)?** *(Open ended)*

• **4. Do you often come close to the maximum occupancy of your space?** *(Select one)*

- Rarely (once a month or less)
- Occasionally (once a week or less)
- Frequently (several time a week)
- Almost always (the place is too small)

Comment

• **5. How many spaces, rooms, or workshops do you operate within the space? How is space distributed for different types of activities (e.g. woodworking area, electronics lab)?** *(Open ended)*

• **6. What materials are commonly used in your space?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Wood
- Plastic
- Metals
- Composites
- Paper/ Cardboard
- Textile
- Biomaterials
- Electronics
- Other *(please specify)*

• Other *(please specify)*

1.2 Machinery and equipment

This section assesses the available equipment and resources in the space and its operational status.

• **7. In what working conditions are your machines and equipment?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Machines are reliable and almost never need repairs
- Machines occasionally break down and need maintenance
- Machines are unreliable and break down often

Comment

• **8. Do your machines and equipment have any special requirements (noise, dust emission, weight, space, safety)?** *(Select all that apply)*

- No special requirements (can be operated without any restrictions)
- Moderate requirements (need of filters, housing)
- Special requirements (safety fence, special filtering system, active emission and noise compensation)

Comment

• **9. Which machines are serviced or maintained in which cycle?** *(Select all that apply then list the machines for each selected category)*

- Weekly
- Monthly
- Every 6 months
- Annually
- As needed

- List your machines that need weekly servicing.

- List your machines that need monthly servicing.

- List your machines that need biannual servicing.

- List your machines that need annual servicing.

- List your machines that are serviced as needed.

Comment

- **10. Are your machine tools multi-functional and support versatility and flexibility in your manufacturing tasks?** *(Select all that apply then list the machines for each selected category)*

- no multi-functionality
- low grade of multi-functionality (e.g. manual change of tool-head possible)
- middle grade of multi-functionality (e.g. automatic tool changer integrated)
- high grade of multi-functionality (e.g. automated material handling unit integrated, automated testing unit integrated)

- List your machines with low grade of multi-functionality.

- List your machines with middle grade of multi-functionality.

- List your machines with high grade of multi-functionality.

- List your mostly automated machines.

- **11. What is the general skill level of the people who operate the machines?** *(Select all that apply then list the machines for each select category)*

- Beginners
- Hobbyists (e.g. able to use a 3D printer)
- Students
- Professionals (e.g. able to use a CNC mill, staff)
- Others *(please specify)*

- What machines are beginners able to use?

- What machines are hobbyists able to use?

- What machines are students able to use?

- What machines are professionals able to use?

- Other *(please specify)*

Comment

12. How intuitive is the operation of your machines for users with varying skill levels (do the machines provide clear instructions of interfaces to assist users during operation...)? *(Scale: 1-5)*

- Please describe.

- **13. How much training is needed to use these machines?** *(Select all that apply then list the machines for each selected category)*

- None, except for basic safety practices
- A one-day introductory course or less
- A multi-day course and regular practice
- Professional training needed

• List the machines that require no training.

• List the machines that require one day of training or less.

• List the machines that require several days of training and practice.

• List the machines that require professional training.

Comment

• **14. Do you use a machine-access-management system to handle bookings, track usage and manage user access?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*

- Yes
- No

• If Yes, please describe.

1.3 Openness of physical equipment

• **15. Do you operate open-source machines (with open-source hardware and/or open-source firmware integrated)?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*

- Yes
- No

• If Yes, were they built in your facility? Describe the machines.

Comment

- **16. Have you ever published/ contributed online schematics, code or instructions for parts design, firmware or even whole machines yourselves?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*

- Yes
- No

- If Yes, please describe briefly which projects, type of contributions, etc...

Comment

- **17. How reliant are you on third parties for the maintenance of your machines?** *(Select one)*

- Very reliant (proprietary tools and components needed, complex machine)
- Moderately reliant (components need to be ordered, but repairable on site)
- Independent (completely repairable with the facility's resources)

Comment

1.4 Manufacturing processes

This section examines the processes and workflows used in the space.

- **18. What type of manufacturing processes are used most frequently in your space?** *(Select all that apply)*

- 3D printing
- CNC milling
- Lasercutting
- Woodworking
- Robotic manufacturing
- Electronic assembly
- Other *(please specify)*

- Other *(please specify)*

- Please describe.

19. How automated are the different listed steps in the manufacturing process in your facility? (Scale : 1-5)

Material storage and transport (within the facility)

Material feeding and setup in the tools or machines

Material processing into components

Component post-processing

Component joining (e.g. welding, gluing)

Component assembly into product

Product packaging

Product transport (within facility) and storage

Comment

1.5 Changeover ability, equipment reconfiguration, adaption and flexibility

This section explores the space's ability to handle varying workloads and adapt to changes.

• **20. What is your current workload or project capacity? (Number of projects per week or per month)**

• **21. Which of these factors is a bottleneck in terms of manufacturing capacity? (Select all that apply)**

- Space occupancy
- Machine occupancy
- Personnel (with needed skills) availability
- Other (please specify)

• If Other (please specify)

22. How easily can you adapt your manufacturing processes to accommodate new projects, changes in demand, or client-specific requests? (Scale: 1-5)

Comment

• **23. Do you track any key performance metrics of your equipment to monitor process success or efficiency? (Yes/No with conditional follow-up)**

- Yes
- No

• If Yes, please describe.

1.6 Energy and sustainability

• **24. What are the main energy sources used in your space? (Select all that apply)**

- Electricity (public grid)
- Electricity (self-generated renewable supply, e.g. solar)
- Gas (public grid)
- Gas (self-generated renewable supply, e.g. biogas)
- Other (please specify)

• Other (please specify)

• **25. Were there, or are there any energy efficiency measures in place? (Yes/No with conditional follow-up)**

- Yes
- No

• If Yes, please describe.

SECTION 2: DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

2.1 Overview of digital tools

This section explores the digital tools and software systems used in the space.

- **26. What are the key digital tools and software systems that you currently use?** *(Select all that apply then list the tools for each selected category)*

- Tool related to space, user and project management (incl. accounting)
- Collaboration tools (communication, (social) networking, match-making)
- Planning and control (e.g. resource-planning tools/ ERP-Systems)
- CAD software (computer-aided design: 2D, 3D, for product design and space layout)
- CAM software (computer-aided manufacturing: incl. CAD-post processor)
- CAE software (computer-aided engineering: programming, analysis, simulation)
- CAQ software (computer-aided quality: quality assessment)
- Machine control software (G-Code interpreter)
- Other *(please specify)*

- Name the management tools in use.

- Name the collaboration tools in use.

- Name the planning tools in use.

- Name the CAD tools in use.

- Name the CAM tools in use.

- Name the CAE tools in use.

- Name the CAQ tools in use.

- Name the machine control softwares in use.

- Other *(please specify)*

27. How integrated are these tools across your operations (e.g. design, production, collaboration with external partners)? *(Scale 1-5, grade each of the following phases)*

Design/development (applies to product/space configuration)

Sourcing

Planning and control

Manufacturing

Quality

Process data tracking

Engineering

Collaboration

Other *(please specify)*

28. What is the level of automation in your digital infrastructure usage/opertaion (e.g. automated data backups, automated file-sharing, workflow automation between design and machines)? (Scale: 1-5)

Comment

• 29. How much training is needed to use these digital tools? (Select all that apply then list the tools for each selected category)

- Very little (common software)
- A one-day introductory course or less
- A multi-day course and regular practice
- Professional training needed (specialist software)

• List the tools that require very little training.

• List the tools that require one day of training or less.

• List the tools that require several days of training and practice.

• List the tools that require professional training.

2.2 Openness of software tools

• 30. Do you use (free and libre) open-source software tools or operating systems or other kinds of programs (e.g. Slicer3D, FreeCAD, Blender, Linux)? (Yes/No with conditional follow up)

- Yes
- No

• If Yes, please specify.

- **31. Have you ever published or contributed to source code and documentation in open-source software projects yourselves (e.g. on Github)?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow up)*

- Yes
- No

- If Yes, please describe briefly which projects, type of contribution, etc.

2.3 Data repositories and management

This section focuses on data storage and accessibility within the space.

- **32. What type of digital repositories do you use for storing project data (e.g. cloud storage like Nextcloud, dropbox, local servers)?** *(Select all that apply)*

- "Cloud" file storage (Google Drive, Dropbox, Nextcloud service)
- Git-based file storages (Github, Gitlab, Forge, etc.)
- MaaS (Manufacturing-as-a-Service) tools (Wikifactory, Siemens Teamcenter, Dassault Systems...)
- Local self-managed servers (with self-managed services)
- Other *(please specify)*

- Name the services.

- Other *(please specify)*

- **33. Is data easily searchable and accessible for all relevant users, team members or external partners?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow up)*

- Yes
- No

- If No, please describe the challenges.

- **34. How is your data access managed and shared?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Different user roles with different access
- Open for everyone to access everything
- Project specific
- No data access and sharing

- **35. What security measures are in place to protect sensitive data (e.g. user authentication, access control, encryption)?** *(Open ended)*

2.4 Digital Product Passport (DPP) capability

- **36. Which of the following data domains do you already gather data from?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Carbon footprint
- Regulatory compliance information
- Lifecycle information for services (repair, disassembly, recycle)
- Other *(please specify)*
- None

- Other *(please specify)*

- **37. How easily do you think the data domains listed above can be tracked?** *(Open ended)*

2.5 Innovation and future readiness

This section assess the space's readiness for adopting new digital technologies.

- **38. How flexible is your current infrastructure to accommodate new technologies (e.g. expanding with AI tools, digital twins, real-time monitoring)?** *(Scale: 1-5)*

If Not flexible, explain.

- **39. How do you stay informed about advancements in digital tools and technologies relevant to your space?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Attending workshops
- Networking with other spaces
- Online research
- Other *(please specify)*

- Other *(please specify)*

SECTION 3: ORGANIZATION OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS

3.1 Manufacturing planning and coordination structure

This section focuses on how manufacturing planning is managed in the spaces.

- **40. How far in advance do you typically plan manufacturing or projects?** *(Select one)*
 - Same day
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - As needed

Comment

- **41. Is project planning integrated with expected client demands or external events?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*
 - Yes
 - No

- If Yes, please specify how planning aligns with these factors.

- **42. Are the people from the design phase involved in production part of the project's design process (to ensure that the project is feasible to produce)?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*
 - Yes
 - No

- If Yes, how are production teams involved?

3.2 Changeover ability of manufacturing processes

This section explores how the space handles flexibility and unexpected changes.

- **43. Is there flexibility built into your project process to handle last-minute changes or unexpected custom orders?** *(Yes/No)*
 - Yes
 - No

- Please describe.

• **44. How often do you make ad-hoc decisions regarding scheduling or resource allocation?** *(Select one)*

- Frequently (weekly)
- Occasionally (monthly)
- Rarely (once a quarter)
- Never

Comment

3.3 Centralized vs. Decentralized vs. Distributed Production

This section assesses whether production is centralized, decentralized or distributed among teams and how information is shared.

• **45. How do you handle external client requests and allocate them to suitable users/members?** *(Select one)*

- Experience based
- Structured with digital tools
- No handling

• Please describe.

• **46. Is project planning and execution centralized, decentralized or distributed?** *(Select one)*

- Centralized (managed and executed by a single person or team)
- Decentralized (separate teams/spaces operating under a common hierarchy)
- Distributed (managed and executed by separate and independent people)

Comment

• **47. Are different types of projects (e.g. woodwork, electronics, 3D printing) managed in separate areas, or is everything done in the same space?** *(Select one)*

- Separate areas for different types of projects
- Same space for all projects

• Please describe.

- **48. How is information shared between teams or project participants?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Digital tools (e.g. shared digital platforms, online meetings)
- In-person meetings (e.g. events, meetings)
- Other (please specify)

- Other *(please specify)*

3.4 Supply chain management

This section explores how materials are sourced and managed.

- **49. How do you manage the flow of materials (e.g. sourcing, inventory, allocation) for projects?** *(Open ended)*

- **50. Are suppliers or material providers integrated into your project planning?** *(Yes/No with conditional follow-up)*

- Yes
- No

- If Yes, please describe.

- **51. How do you manage material shortages or delays in sourcing materials?** *(Open ended)*

- **52. Have you applied any circular economy practices regarding manufacturing and the use of materials?** *(Select all that apply then describe your practices for each selected answer)*

- Reducing material waste (e.g. optimization of offcuts, additive manufacturing)
- Reducing energy consumption ((e.g. optimization of machine run time)
- Reducing need for material (through eco-design)
- Reducing use of non-recyclable/non-biodegradable materials
- Reducing use of virgin material, increasing use of recycled material
- Repurposing used components into new products (cannibalizing, upcycling)
- Refurbishing and upgrading older products to fit your needs
- Using locally sourced materials (virgin or recycled)
- Manufacturing waste sorting
- In-house manufacturing waste recycling/recovery
- Opportunistic or agreed sharing of waste (as raw material) between local businesses
- Other *(please specify)*

Describe your practices regarding the reduction of material waste.

Describe your practices regarding the reduction of energy consumption?

Describe your practices regarding the reduction in need for material.

Describe your practices regarding the reduction in use of non-recyclable/non-biodegradable materials.

Describe your practices regarding the reduction in use of virgin material or increased use of recycled material.

Describe your practices regarding component repurposing.

Describe your practices regarding product refurbishment and upgrading.

Describe your practices regarding the use of locally sourced materials.

Describe your practices regarding the sorting of manufacturing waste.

Describe your practices regarding the recycling/recovery of manufacturing waste.

Describe your practices regarding the sharing of waste as raw material (urban mining).

Other *(please specify)*

• **53. Are there any circular economy considerations during the design phase regarding the life cycle of your products?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Increasing the product's physical lifespan (e.g. durability, repairability, not applicable to consumable products)
- Increasing the product's functional lifespan (e.g. high added value, upgradeability, modular design, if relevant)
- Refusing to build a product in the first place if it's function is redundant
- Recycling-optimized designs (e.g. mono-material sub-assemblies)
- Product-service systems (e.g. integration of circular services linked to the design)
- Other *(please specify)*

• Other *(please specify)*

3.5 Quality control and process improvement

This section focuses on quality assurance processes and how defects or issues are managed.

• **54. What quality control measures are in place to ensure that projects meet design and performance requirements?** *(Select all that apply)*

- Testing of prototypes with self-defined criteria
- Peer review by other members
- External feedback from for example potential users or professionals
- Other *(please specify)*

• Other *(please specify)*

• Please describe.

• **55. How do you handle defects or quality issues (e.g. rework, redesign, collaboration with the client /partner)? Do you track any quality metrics for completed projects (e.g. number of reworks, customer feedback)?** *(Open ended)*

3.6 Knowledge management

- **56. What type of requirements regarding users' skills and knowledge for using your space and equipment do you use? How do you know which user has which needed skills? (Select one)**

- Trust base, no formal requirements
- Certification (users need to show that they did training)
- Other (please specify)

- Other (please specify)

3.7 Challenges and future considerations

This section identifies challenges and opportunities for improving the production process.

- **57. What are the biggest challenges you face in managing the manufacturing process? (Select all that apply)**

- Demand variability
- Equipment capabilities
- Equipment capacities
- Coordination among teams
- Material availability
- Other (please specify)

- Other (please specify)

- **58. What are the primary opportunities for improving how your space organizes and manages manufacturing? (Select all that apply)**

- More multi-functional tools
- More userfriendly tools
- More skilled staff
- Improved workflows
- Better coordination with external partners
- Better coordination with internal team/users
- Improved space usage
- Other (please specify)

- Other (please specify)

Appendix 2.b Survey questionnaire - Interview

SECTION 1: PHYSICAL CAPABILITIES

1.1 General Overview

Q1 Could you briefly describe one example of small-batch production in your space: what kind of product, batch size, which materials used, which machines used, what end-customer, what type of user?

1.2 Machinery and Equipment

Q2 What are the most common breakdowns in your equipment setup?

Q3 Are all manufacturing services and maintenance done internally or are any external services in use?

1.3 Openness of Physical Equipment

Q4 What opportunities and challenges do you see in using open-source hardware equipment (like machine tools)?

1.4 Technology and Innovation

Q5 Are there any new tools, machines, or technologies (hardware related) that could support your operations and improve your space's capabilities?

1.5 Manufacturing Processes

Q6 Could you describe your grade of automation in your manufacturing processes (from material handling, machining until distribution)?

Q7 How often do you explore and test new manufacturing methods or processes (e.g. lean prototyping, agile design, open manufacturing, etc.) to enhance your space's operations?

1.6 Changeover Ability, Equipment Reconfiguration, Adaption and Flexibility

Q8 Could you describe in more detail your bottlenecks or inefficiencies in your workflow that limit your ability to take on more projects or larger tasks?

Q9 Could you easily expand your capacity with additional resources?

Q10 Are your machines' operations flexible in adapting to new and diverse projects (e.g. the machine allows you to quickly iterate, it had a large build volume, etc.)?

1.7 Energy and Sustainability

Q11 Were there, or are there any energy-efficiency or sustainability measures analyzed or considered?

1.8 Innovation and Future Readiness

Q12 Do you have any plans to expand your space capabilities (e.g. more machines, expanded space, more complex projects)?

Q13 Do you foresee any changes in the industry or community that might impact how you operate?

Q14 Do you face any challenges from external factors that affect your physical capabilities?

SECTION 2: DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

2.1 General Overview

Q15 Are there any "advanced" digital tools/services used in project scheduling, operation and/or maintenance (e.g., AI for analysis, predictive maintenance of machines)?

2.2 Openness of Software Tools

Q16 Are there any future plans to adopt or expand the use of open-source software tools? Why? Why not?

2.3 Data Repositories and Management

Q17 Are there any challenges/inefficiencies you are facing with the handling/use of digital tools and data management (e.g. compatibility issues between tools and files, lack of tech savvy people)?

2.4 Collaboration and Communication Tools

Q18 Are there any communication or collaboration challenges that the current digital tools do not address?

2.5 Innovation and Future Readiness

Q19 Are there any plans for future investments in digital infrastructure (e.g. AI, advanced design tools, IoT devices, machine learning)?
Q20 How flexible is your current infrastructure to accommodate new digital technologies (e.g., expanding with AI tools, digital twins, real-time monitoring)?

Q20 What challenges do you foresee in scaling your digital infrastructure (e.g. cost, technical complexity, user training)?

SECTION 3: ORGANIZATION OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS

3.1 Manufacturing Planning and Coordination Structure

Q21 Could you describe how you plan and schedule your projects (e.g. what tools, documents or methods do you use) and how do you manage and allocate resources (e.g. machines, materials, people) when planning projects?

Q22 How do you ensure alignment between production, material sourcing and the availability of machines or tools?

3.2 Changeover Ability of Manufacturing Processes:

Q25 Do you often face last-minute changes or unexpected custom orders, urgent or rush projects (e.g. urgent client requests, last-minute community events) and how do you handle these?

Q26 If applicable, how do you ensure that ad hoc decisions (e.g. re-prioritizing projects) don't negatively impact overall project flow or quality?

3.6 Knowledge Management

Q27 How do you manage existing manufacturing experience and knowledge developed over time?

3.7 Challenges and Future Considerations

Q28 How do you plan to improve your changeover ability (flexibility) to adapt your manufacturing processes to external changes (e.g. changes in client's demand, material availability)?

Q29 Are there plans to restructure or improve your manufacturing management in the near future?

**Technische Universität Berlin / Grenoble Inp Université
Grenoble Alpes / Helmut Schmidt Universität
Universität der Bundeswehr Hamburg / Université de
Lorraine / Zentrum für Soziale Innovation Gmbh Inova+
Innovation Services, S.A / Maker / Stichting Dyne.Org /
Bauhaus-Universität Weimar / Fab City Hamburg
E.V.Hiww Ug / SUPSI University of Applied Sciences and
Arts of Southern Switzerland**

LAUDS Local Accessible Urban Digital Sustainable Factories is a Horizon Europe research and innovation action - Co-funded by the European Union, 2024-2026, GA 101135986

